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Report on EPC data analysis

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Table of contents

1 Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose and target group	7
1.2 Deliverable structure	7
1.3 Contribution of partners.....	8
1.4 Relations to other project activities	8
2 Research methodology	9
2.1 Purpose	9
2.2 Methods and tools	9
2.3 Participants	10
2.4 Implementation	10
2.5 Limitations	10
3 Literature review on EPC data quality	12
4 Comparative analysis of EPC data	14
4.1 Data collection sheet	14
4.2 Comparison tables	20
5 Deficiencies and potential improvements on EPC data quality and contents	27
5.1 Input data for the building EP assessment	27
5.2 EP assessment methods and related outputs	34
5.3 Current approaches for data quality control	38
6 Relation to other tasks	42
7 Conclusions	44
References	46
Annexes	49
Annex A - Data collection sheets of each participating country	49
Annex B - Comparison tables	61
Annex C - Key terms and definitions	75

List of tables

Table 1. Data collection sheet overview (Part 1)	15
Table 2. Data collection sheet overview (Part 2)	16
Table 3. Overview of the <i>Contents</i> section of the data collection sheet	17
Table 4. Overview of the <i>Data sources</i> section of the data collection sheet.....	18
Table 5. Overview of the <i>Data quality</i> section of the data collection sheet	19
Table 6. <i>Suggested level of uncertainty</i> matrix	19
Table 7. Overview of the <i>Data applications</i> section of the data collection sheet.....	20
Table 8. <i>EPC data availability</i> comparison table (extract)	21
Table 9. <i>Data source and determination</i> comparison table	23
Table 10. <i>Data source and determination</i> comparison table - detail of data by country (extract) ..	23
Table 11. <i>Input accuracy</i> comparison table (extract)	25
Table 12. <i>Overview of applications</i> comparison table (extract)	26
Table 13. Recommendations based on outcomes of Task 1.3 and related TDSs (WP2).....	42
Table 14. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Austria)	49
Table 15. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Austria)	50
Table 16. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Croatia).....	51
Table 17. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Croatia).....	52
Table 18. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Cyprus).....	53
Table 19. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Cyprus).....	54
Table 20. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Italy)	55
Table 21. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Italy)	56
Table 22. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Slovenia).....	57
Table 23. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Slovenia).....	58
Table 24. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Spain)	59
Table 25. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Spain)	60
Table 26. <i>EPC data availability</i> comparison table (Part 1).....	61
Table 27. <i>EPC data availability</i> comparison table (Part 2)	62
Table 28. <i>EPC data availability</i> comparison table (Part 3).....	63
Table 29. <i>EPC data availability</i> comparison table (Part 4).....	64
Table 30. <i>Data source and determination</i> comparison table - detail of data by country (Part 1) ...	65
Table 31. <i>Data source and determination</i> comparison table - detail of data by country (Part 2) ...	66
Table 32. <i>Input accuracy</i> comparison table (Part 1).....	67
Table 33. <i>Input accuracy</i> comparison table (Part 2).....	68
Table 34. <i>Input accuracy</i> comparison table (Part 3).....	69

Table 35. <i>Input accuracy</i> comparison table (Part 4)	70
Table 36. <i>Overview of applications</i> comparison table (Part 1)	71
Table 37. <i>Overview of applications</i> comparison table (Part 2)	72
Table 38. <i>Overview of applications</i> comparison table (Part 3)	73
Table 39. <i>Overview of applications</i> comparison table (Part 4)	74

List of figures

Figure 1. Relationships between the data collection sheet and the comparison tables (research topics) in the overall EPC context analysis devised in TIMEPAC	9
Figure 2. Percentage of the EPC data available compared to the whole information, by country... 21	
Figure 3. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - all countries	24
Figure 4. Percentage of EPC data exploited in each country by type of application	26
Figure 5. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Austria ..	28
Figure 6. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Croatia..	29
Figure 7. Input data to model the photovoltaic system in SBEM (SBEM, 2014) (1)	29
Figure 8. Input data to model the photovoltaic system in SBEM (SBEM, 2014) (2)	30
Figure 9. Interface of SBEM (SBEM, 2014)	30
Figure 10. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Cyprus ..	31
Figure 11. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Italy	32
Figure 12. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Slovenia	33
Figure 13. Number of occurrences of <i>Source type</i> and <i>Way of determination</i> , and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Spain	34
Figure 14. Sample of a section of an EPC report for Cyprus	36
Figure 15. Relationship between the outcomes of the comparison tables and the objectives of the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs) of TIMEPAC	42

Executive Summary

The present deliverable, D1.3, relates to the work performed in Task 1.3 of TIMEPAC. Task 1.3 is part of Work Package 1 (WP1), which is aimed at carrying out a comparative study of the elements involved in the energy performance certification (EPC) data flow devised in TIMEPAC, i.e., generation, storage, analysis and exploitation. Work Package 1 concerns the context analysis that supports the EPC workflow; it allows to identify potential improvements, vulnerabilities, threats and risks related to the upgrade of the already existing energy performance certification schemes. Task 1.3 focuses on one of the EPC data flow elements, namely the EPC data analysis. In this task, deficiencies and potential improvements of current EPC data quality across participating countries are identified.

On the national/regional level, the TIMEPAC partners analysed and compared the EPC data – in terms of input and output data – and collected the necessary information to analyse the input data quality, in terms of data sources and ways of data determination. Information on the existing certification tools and/or protocols to validate the EPC data is provided, as well as the current procedures, methods, instruments that detect essential data quality issues in the participating countries/regions (i.e., Austria-Province of Salzburg, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy-Regione Piemonte, Slovenia, Spain-Catalonia).

A methodology was followed to collect and compare data between the involved countries/regions, based on the use of a data *collection sheet* and *comparison tables*. The data collection sheet was structured in such a way to gather information from partners through a *bottom-up* approach that follows a comprehensive collection of the available data.

The comparison tables were suitable to compare the information provided by the participating countries/regions (cross-country comparison) on the following research topics: “EPC data availability”, “Data source and determination”, “Input accuracy”, and “Overview of applications”. The tables are interrelated, i.e., the information coming from a table affects or is related to the subsequent one. In addition, the starting point (“EPC data availability”) and the ending point (“Overview of applications”) are strictly related to the elements of the EPC data flow placed just before and after the EPC data analysis, i.e., the EPC storage and the EPC exploitation, respectively.

The outcomes of the context analysis on the EPC data quality and availability inform the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs) of TIMEPAC that are aimed at developing and delivering new methods to implement enhanced EPC schemas in WP2. The potential improvements outlined in Task 1.3 and the related TDSs are listed as follows:

- To expand the set of energy performance (EP) indicators in the EPC (operational data, costs, IEQ aspects, etc.) (TDS 2),
- To integrate the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) in the EPC (TDS 4),
- To create guidelines for EPC generation from Building Information Modelling (BIM) data (TDS 1),
- To enhance EPC with information from inspection of technical building systems and other building related data (TDS 3),
- To foster the generation of EPCs from BIM models (TDS 1),
- To improve the accuracy and reproducibility of the whole EP assessment procedures (TDS 2),
- To check quality of the EPC data (TDS 5),
- To generate Building Renovation Passport (BRP) from EPC data (TDS 3),
- To exploit the EPC for carrying out energy balances of the building stocks (TDS 5).

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and target group

The present deliverable concerns the activity carried out in Task 1.3 that is part of Work Package 1 (WP1) of the TIMEPAC project. WP1 is aimed at carrying out a comparative study of the elements involved in the energy performance certification (EPC) data flow devised in TIMEPAC, i.e., generation, storage, analysis and exploitation. Work Package 1 concerns the context analysis that supports the EPC workflow; it allows to identify potential improvements, vulnerabilities, threats and risks related to the upgrade of the already existing energy performance certification schemes. The outcomes of WP1 will be used as baseline for the new enhanced certification schemes resulting from the methods deployed and delivered in Work Package 2 (WP2), through the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs), and then implemented in the Demonstration Scenarios (DSs) carried out in Work Package 3 (WP3).

Task 1.3 focuses on one of the EPC data flow elements, namely the EPC data analysis. In this task, deficiencies and potential improvements of current EPC data quality across participating countries are identified. On the national/regional level, the TIMEPAC partners analysed and compared the EPC data – in terms of input and output data – and collected the necessary information by means of a *data collection sheet* to analyse the input data quality, in terms of data sources and ways of data determination. The produced output data highlight the quality of the energy performance indicators included in the EPC schema. Information on the existing certification tools and/or protocols to validate the EPC data is provided, as well as the current procedures, methods, instruments that detect essential data quality issues in the participating countries.

A focus is on the current application of EPC data at national/regional scale, so as to address the enhancement of the data availability and the introduction of new indicators in the EPC schema, and to improve the data quality for specific energy related domains. Pilot partners will understand what types of data need an increase of accuracy and what new information is necessary in the future to enhance the EPC schema and its effectiveness through exploitation.

The outcomes of Task 1.3 will help to properly define guidelines for the implementation of the continuous EPC workflow elaborated in Task 1.5.

1.2 Deliverable structure

The present deliverable has been structured into seven main sections, as follows.

Section 1 provides the introduction, focusing on: the objective of Task 1.3 (1.1), the deliverable structure (1.2), the contribution of the TIMEPAC partners (1.3), and the relations to the other project activities (1.4). Section 2 focuses on the research approach followed in TIMEPAC to collect information on EPC data and the main outcomes. Section 3 deals with a literature review on the topic of EPC data analysis and focuses on the current research studies on EPC data quality, highlighting the main research gaps which TIMEPAC is going to address. Section 4 presents the *data collection sheet*, providing a detailed description of its content (4.1). To analyse the information gathered from partners, a cross-country comparison was carried out through the *comparison tables*, whose contents and results are discussed (4.2). Section 5 highlights deficiencies and potential improvements on EPC data contents and quality, starting from the outcomes of the comparison tables. A description is provided for each involved country/region on the following aspects: input data for the building EP assessment (5.1), EP assessment methods and related outputs (5.2), and current approaches for data quality control (5.3). Final recommendations are provided as to guide the subsequent development of TIMEPAC; relations to other project activities are devised accordingly (Section 6). Section 7 provides the conclusions.

1.3 Contribution of partners

The EPC data analysis was carried out by POLITO with the contribution of the TIMEPAC consortium. Specifically, the project partners, grouped by participating country/region, provided the necessary information by filling in the data collection sheet, discussing the outcomes of the comparison tables, and providing inputs in Section 5 in the country dedicated sub-sections.

1.4 Relations to other project activities

Task 1.3 addresses the EPC data analysis which is one of the four phases of the EPC data flow devised in TIMEPAC and has relations to the other phases, as follows.

- EPC generation (Task 1.1). The generation process of an EPC was analysed as it affects data quality.
- EPC storage (Task 1.2). The EPC data availability was investigated in terms of different existing databases.
- EPC exploitation (Task 1.4). The data quality was assessed keeping in mind the possible levels of EPC exploitation.

The outputs of the analysis carried out in this task will help WP2 tasks to understand what they will address to increase data availability and reduce data uncertainty (increased level of quality).

2 Research methodology

2.1 Purpose

To attain the objectives provided for in Task 1.3 of TIMEPAC, a research approach was devised. It was structured into two main phases, in order to collect, process and discuss the EPC data.

According to the EPC data analysis introduced in Section 1.1 of the present deliverable, each of the two phases of the research is focused on developing a specific sub-task. The first one focuses on the information about EPC data availability (i.e., contents), data sources, data quality, and data application. Starting from the outcomes of the first part, the second phase of the research was aimed to assess the deficiencies and potential improvements on EPC input data. The information picture was then completed by addressing some specific aspects, related to the current assessment methods of the building energy performance – which affect the accuracy of the calculation outputs – and, the current approaches for data quality control.

2.2 Methods and tools

To the final aim of harmonising the data analysis in the EPC workflow devised in TIMEPAC, the collection and the processing of EPC data was carried out by means of a *data collection sheet* and *comparison tables*, respectively. The data collection sheet was structured in such a way to gather information at national/regional level through a bottom-up approach that follows a comprehensive collection of the available data. The comparison tables are suitable to compare the information provided by the participating countries/regions (cross-country comparison) in an effective way.

Both the data collection sheet and the comparison tables were developed on MS Excel spreadsheets.

The data collection sheet is organised into four investigation areas: contents, data sources, data quality, and data application. Each area allows to collect and organise a different package of information. Then, four comparison tables are devised, each one focusing on a specific research topic, such as *EPC data availability*, *Data source and determination*, *Input accuracy*, and *Overview of applications*. Each topic delivers specific information that originates from a different aggregation of the fields of the data collection sheet, as outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Relationships between the data collection sheet and the comparison tables (research topics) in the overall EPC context analysis devised in TIMEPAC

The data collection sheets and the comparison tables can be considered the key-instruments for the EPC data analysis that is one of the four elements of the EPC data flow devised in TIMEPAC. In addition, the topics presented by the tables are interrelated; the starting point (*EPC data availability*) and the ending point (*Overview of applications*) are strictly related to the elements of the EPC data flow placed just before and after the EPC data analysis, i.e. the EPC storage and the EPC exploitation, respectively, as also shown in Figure 1.

More insights on data collection sheet and comparison tables are provided in Section 4 together with their application in the project context.

2.3 Participants

The data collection sheet was filled in by the pilot partners who are responsible of the EPC database of their country/region. The profile of the persons who participated in the study were experts in energy efficiency of buildings. The same experts oversaw the content of Sections 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. The cross-country comparison was performed by academic researchers in the field of building physics and building energy systems.

2.4 Implementation

The methodological approach followed to carry out the EPC data analysis was elaborated considering a total of six pilot cases, one for each partner of the project. These are responsible for the management and assessment of EPC data in different countries and regions of Europe: Salzburg (Austria), Croatia, Cyprus, Piemonte (Italy), Slovenia, and Catalonia (Spain).

The methodology developed consists of the following connected tasks:

1. Gathering of information on EPC data by means of the data collection sheet (one for each country/region).
2. Processing of information on EPC data by means of the comparison tables (one for a different research topic).
3. Collecting of information (textual support) to close the information picture.

The challenge was to generate a valid overall picture suitable for comparison and gap analysis, without being distracted by the different approaches which are used in all partner countries. Partners were required to strike a balance and to focus their contributions on the most relevant aspects in the context of the project.

2.5 Limitations

EPC data analysis was carried out by pilot partners which represent a limited number of EU Member States. In addition, two contributions refer to regions and not to the entire country because there is a regional implementation of energy performance certification (Piemonte/Italy and Catalonia/Spain). In Italy, the focus is on Piemonte region, but since the EPC schema and the building EP calculation methodology are harmonized nationally, the outcomes of this analysis can be considered valid for the whole Italian country. In Spain, the EPC schema and legislation are common for all the regions. The management of the registers is regional. In Catalonia, the EPC information (excluded personal data) is public and available in Open Data databases. In Austria, there is a regional implementation, as well, and the province of Salzburg contributes to the TIMEPAC project as Austrian pilot. However, there is also a harmonised approach for many aspects at federal level, and therefore the Austrian contribution to this task is at country level where possible. Despite these limitations in terms of quantitative representativeness, the results offer a qualitative insight that is entirely sufficient in the context of the project.

At consortium level, although a guideline was developed to explain the data collection sheet, there remains a range of interpretation of the terminology used, which is determined by national/regional

practice and possibly different approaches depending on building type, timing of issuing the energy certificate during the life cycle of the building (new construction, renovation, sale or rental) and other aspects. As a result, depending on the situation in the partner countries, the answers may represent an expert opinion summarising the different options.

To clarify the meaning of the terms frequently used in this context, a terminology section is provided in Annex C.

3 Literature review on EPC data quality

The European directive 2002/91/EC (European Parliament, 2002) established the introduction of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) as a mandatory requirement for constructed, sold, or rented out buildings. The EPC represents a core source of information that reflects the energy performance status of the building stocks, the fuel poverty of a specific country, and the monitoring of national or regional energy renovation programs (Hardy & Glew, 2019). Therefore, the data quality of certificates influences the reliability, adequacy, plausibility, coherence, and accuracy – considered as the reduction of the uncertainty¹ – of the information stored. The main aspects that reflect on the EPC data quality are related to the accuracy of the input data, the methodology and software applied, and the energy assessors' qualification (Li et al., 2019). However, the knowledge and the experience of the technician in charge to carry out the EPC is the main factor that affects the data quality of the certificate. Tronchin & Fabbri (2012) have set up a round-robin test to evaluate the expertise of 162 technicians to estimate the energy performance of the same building. All the independent experts have had the same inputs and were beginners on the software to be used. The experiment revealed that approximately 70% of energy assessors had correctly estimated the energy rating of the building assessed. Certainly, the aforementioned percentage can be influenced by the energy tool chosen by the independent experts. However, in Italy, this issue has been overcome as the software to calculate the energy performance of buildings is validated by the Italian Thermotechnical Committee (CTI) and presents a maximum deviation of $\pm 5\%$ compared to the corresponding energy indicators determined through technical standards (Italian Republic, 2015). So, the test of Tronchin & Fabbri (2012) clearly showed that the qualification of the technician in charge is essential for the quality of the EPC. In this context, the collection and the validation of the input data represent a basic skill to correctly conduct the subsequent energy certification phases.

The EPBD-recast (European Parliament, 2010), amended by Directive no. 844 of 2018 (European Parliament, 2018), allows Member States ample degrees of freedom in the definition of the energy performance calculation methodologies. As described by Zirngibl & Bendžalová (2015), in the European Member States thirty-five different methodologies to assess the energy performance of buildings have been introduced. Semple & Jenkins (2020) reviewed the energy performance assessment calculation methodology for six European countries: the UK, France, Germany, Spain, Italy, and Poland. The analysis was focused on the thermal transmittance values of the building envelope – proposed by the national technical standard and considered as a key parameter in the energy performance calculation – to reason about (in-)consistency between countries. Andaloro et al. (2010), instead, discussed the lack of harmonisation in the energy certificate framework in the European countries. The analysis was carried out by setting two different indicators to score various aspects related to the EPC generation. However, increased accuracy due to the introduction of a new methodology to generate the EPC contents does not necessarily imply an improvement in data quality if applied incorrectly or by unqualified energy assessors. Arcipowska et al. (2015), instead, proposed an overview of the Member States' different accreditation procedures to qualify independent experts.

Moreover, according to literature, better accuracy and reliability of EPC information derive from the following aspects:

- **Sustainability indicators:** EPC is an energy-related document based on the determination of the EP indicator. However, the improvement of certificates should be even more focused on social, environmental, and economical aspects. Tsatsakis et al. (2017) suggested transforming static EPC information into a dynamic entity introducing real-consumption data. The cost-effective energy efficiency measures which are technologically and

¹ See Annex C - Key terms and definitions.

economically feasible should be provided in the EPC to guide the end-user in the renovation of building (Caceres, 2018). Although Parkinson et al. (2013) studied how the energy rating of a building reflects the satisfaction of occupants, in the EPC there is an information deficiency about the indoor environmental quality. According to Zuhair et al. (2021), new energy indicators must be integrated into the next certificate generation: the smart readiness indicator (European Commission, 2020), i.e., the capability of the technical building systems to adapt their operation to the needs of the occupants; indexes that represent the indoor and outdoor air quality; real consumption information; and an indicator that informs end-user about benefits to connecting the building to a district heating or cooling system. Anagnostopoulos et al. (2015) suggested to highlight fiscal incentive programmes in the EPCs, as to encourage the occupants' awareness about renovation activities.

- **Data interoperability:** Interoperability of data is one of the key pillars of the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse; Wilkinson et al., 2016). Data could be expressed in various forms, but it must be considered as a unique entity linked to different databases (i.e., EPC database, cadastre database, statistical database, geographical database, etc.). To improve data quality, ownership of information should belong to a single-centralized system that communicates with the others.
- **Database control activities:** Each EPC database should have its analysis technique to detect anomalous data (Hardy & Glew, 2019; Prieler et al., 2017). Pasichnyi et al. (2019) proposed six different levels to validate EPC data quality. A virtuous case of preventive control activities on EPC data quality is the database of the Italian region Emilia-Romagna, that has two steps of examinations regarding the documents stored (Marinosci & Morini, 2014). The first level of the first examination (type A) is focused on preventive online control activities addressed to guide the energy assessor to upload EPC with plausible numbers and without technical inconsistency. This kind of check improves the data quality of the EPC, minimising typing errors.
- **Cost adaptation:** EPC data quality is even influenced by the market laws. Croatia, Denmark, Hungary, and Slovenia have a standardized price regulation to produce the energy certification. The report of Arcipowska et al. (2015) presents EPC range-prices for single-family-houses for twelve European countries.
- **Independent controls reinforcement:** EPBD-recast (European Parliament, 2018) declares that the Member States have to reinforce control measures to improve the data quality of the EPCs. In Italy, according to the Ministerial Decree of 26 June 2015 (Italian Republic, 2015), at least 2% of the energy certificates deposited must be checked by competent bodies.

European harmonisation of the minimum qualification level of an energy assessor, of the energy performance calculation methodology, and of the data stored in the certificate are fundamental requirements to homogenize and to align the EPC framework and content around European countries. High EPC data quality is a necessary condition to have a clear picture of the energy status of the building stock and to improve the knowledge and awareness on energy efficiency.

4 Comparative analysis of EPC data

In the present section, the application of the methodology developed in Task 1.3 of TIMEPAC is presented, as well as the outcomes of the EPC data analysis. This section deals with the first research phase, as introduced in Section 2.1.

4.1 Data collection sheet

A data collection sheet was developed in order to gather EPC data from the TIMEPAC country partners. The data collection sheet, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2, allows to list each datum included in the EPC and to provide information about it. Such information has been organised into four investigation areas: contents (in light orange), data sources (in light blue), data quality (in grey), and data application (in green). The ways to fill in the sheet include free text, single choice from a list, true or false answer; some cells are automatically compiled.

The list of EPC data is divided into six groups, as follows:

- EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor.
- General information about the building.
- EPC information on building at the current state.
- EPC information on technical building systems at the current state.
- EPC results.
- EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations).

For each datum, the identifying name and a brief description is offered for the purpose of clarifying the required information.

A base list of EPC data with the name, the description and the data category has been suggested and is common to all country partners; these cells, like the ones not meant to be filled in by the user, are grey coloured. In order to give the partners the possibility to add any datum which is missing in the suggested list, a second table named “Additional EPC data” is provided in the bottom part of the sheet.

In the following subsections, a detailed description of the information delivered by the data collection sheet by investigation area is provided.

An overview of the Data collection sheet can be seen in Tables 1 and 2. Annex A includes the complete sheets released by the involved countries.

Table 1. Data collection sheet overview (Part 1)

	Contents						Data sources			Data quality			Data applications						
	Name	Description	Content database			Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XbE database	Availability of the content in the open access database														
	Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XbE database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme	Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation	Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty		True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)		
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>			<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment							General										
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)							General										
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model							General										
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge							General										
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC							General										
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude							Geographical information										
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building							Geographical information										
	Cadastral information	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank							General										
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building							General										
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)							General										
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)							General										
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements							General										
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building							General										
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building							General										
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building							General										
	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located							Climatic data										
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)							Climatic data										
EPC information on building at the current state	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone							Geometric										
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building							Geometric										
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume							Geometric										
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment							Geometric										
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment							Geometric										
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment							Geometric										
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)							Geometric										
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area							Building fabric										
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area							Building fabric										
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area							Building fabric										
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature							Building fabric										
	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)							Building fabric										
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation							Building fabric											
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.							Technical building systems										
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)							Technical building systems										
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service							Technical building systems										
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service							Technical building systems										
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service							Technical building systems										
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)							Technical building systems										
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service							Technical building systems										

Table 2. Data collection sheet overview (Part 2)

	Contents									Data sources			Data quality			Data applications				
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
	<i>Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)</i>	<i>Brief description of the parameter</i>						<i>Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation</i> <i>Output to be used only for final results</i>					<i>Automatic filled</i> <i>Level of uncertainty required only for input data</i>	<i>Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty</i> <i>Level of uncertainty required only for input data</i> <i>Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty</i> <i>Leave blank if the cell is grey</i>		<i>True (-) False (X)</i>	<i>True (-) False (X)</i>	<i>True (-) False (X)</i>		
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>
EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time					Energy indicators													
	Energy need for space cooling	Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time					Energy indicators													
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area					Energy indicators													
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area					Energy indicators													
	Delivered energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the exported energy					Energy indicators													
	Exported energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary					Energy indicators													
	Exported energy carrier type	Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary					Energy indicators													
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building					Energy indicators													
	CO ₂ emissions	Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace					Environmental indicators													
	SRI indicators	The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid					Energy indicators													
	NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB					Energy indicators													
Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values					Energy indicators														
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions					General													
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM					Energy indicators													
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM					Energy indicators													
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofitting options					Economic informations													
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment					General													
Additional EPC data																				

4.1.1 Contents

The *Contents* section of the data collection sheet (Table 3) includes the general information regarding each EPC datum; the following inputs are required:

- *Name*, which is pre-compiled and contains the name of the datum.
- *Description*, which is pre-compiled and contains the description of the datum.
- *Content database*, which is divided into four sections; in the first one, it is required to define whether the datum is available or not, while in the following three sections, it is required to specify in which database the datum is available, i.e., the XML file, the open access database, and the EPC scheme, respectively.
- *Data category*, which is pre-compiled and specifies the category of the datum, i.e., general, geographic information, geometric, building fabric, technical building systems, energy indicators, environmental indicators, climatic data, economic indicators.
- *Type*, which specifies whether the datum is defined as a number, “Quantitative”, or not, “Qualitative”.
- *Input or output for energy calculation*, which is required only for the data that take part in the building energy performance assessment, otherwise the field should be left empty; dependently on the datum specificity, it can be marked with “Input”, “Intermediate result” or “Output”.

Any further clarifying information can be provided in the *Notes* column.

Table 3. Overview of the *Contents* section of the data collection sheet

Contents									
Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes
Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database True (✓) False (X) (optional)	Availability of the content in the open access database True (✓) False (X) (optional)	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme True (✓) False (X) (optional)			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results	
<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>

4.1.2 Data sources

The *Data sources* section (Table 4) contains the information regarding the origin and the determination of the datum; the following two inputs are required:

- *Source type*, which specifies the source of the datum.
- *Way of determination*, which specifies the way used to produce the datum, strictly related to the source type.

The *Source type* can be chosen from a list of possible entries, as follows:

- *Cadastral database*, which is a database of cadastral information, including value and ownership of real estate.
- *Geographic database*, which is a database including the geographic coordinates of the assessed object.

TIMEPAC D1.3 - Comparative analysis of EPC data

- *Regional or national database*, which is a database managed by regional or national authorities.
- *Statistical database*, which is a database based on statistical surveys.
- *Survey on-site*, which concerns data collected by the assessor in charge during the survey on the assessed object.
- *Technician defined*, which concerns data defined by the technician in charge based on his/her experience or knowledge.
- *Legislative or technical standard*, which concerns data extracted by legislative or technical standards.
- *Based on occupant interview*, which concerns data derived from occupant interviews or questionnaires.
- *Existing energy report*, which concerns data obtained from existing energy report on the assessed object (e.g., previous EPC, energy audit, etc.).
- *Numerical assessment*, which concerns data derived from calculation.
- *Energy bills*, which concern data extracted from energy bills.

The *Way of determination* can be chosen from a list of possible entries, as follows:

- *inspection*, which is a procedure to collect information on-site,
- *detailed calculation*, which is referred to a detailed hourly or sub-hourly method for energy calculation,
- *simplified calculation*, which is referred to a calculation based on procedures presented in European or national technical standards (e.g., quasi-steady-state methods for energy calculation),
- *measurement / monitoring*, which refers to data measured or monitored on-site,
- *technician assumption*, which refers to assumptions made by a technician based on his/her experience or knowledge,
- *external reference*, which concerns a source provided by regional or national authorities.

Any further clarifying information can be provided in the *Notes* column.

Table 4. Overview of the *Data sources* section of the data collection sheet

<i>Data sources</i>		
Source type	Way of determination	Notes
<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Free text>

4.1.3 Data quality

The *Data quality* section of the data collection sheet (Table 5) addresses the accuracy of input data (i.e., the data marked as “Input” in the “Input or output for energy calculation” field of the *Contents* section). The output and intermediate results of the energy calculation procedure are function of both the input data accuracy and the calculation method used for the building energy performance assessment. In the first phase of the research, the focus was only done on the quality of the input data, while the accuracy of the calculation method was addressed in the second phase (Section 5.2 of the present deliverable).

TIMEPAC D1.3 - Comparative analysis of EPC data

For each input, the requests are listed as follows:

- *Suggested level of uncertainty*, which represents a plausible level of uncertainty based on the *Source type* and the *Way of determination* as selected in the *Data sources* section. It is a pre-compiled field, determined as presented below.
- *Level of uncertainty*, which can be manually provided in case the *Suggested level of uncertainty* does not fit the actual accuracy of the datum.

Table 5. Overview of the *Data quality* section of the data collection sheet

<i>Data quality</i>		
Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes
Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey	
<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>

Table 6. *Suggested level of uncertainty* matrix

		WAY OF DETERMINATION						
		Inspection	Detailed calculation	Simplified calculation	Measurement / Monitoring	Technician assumption	External reference	NA
SOURCE TYPE	Cadastre database	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check
	Geographical database	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check
	Regional or national database	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check
	Statistical database	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check
	Survey on-site	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	Technician defined	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 2	Level 1	Level 2	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	Legislative or technical standard	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 2	Level 3	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	Based on occupant interview	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	Existing energy report	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 2	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	Numerical assessment	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Level 1	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	Energy bills	Level 2	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Level 3	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	Inconsistency between source type and way of determination, please check	No suggested level of uncertainty is available
	NA	No suggested level of uncertainty is available						

The *Suggested level of uncertainty* originates from the combination of *Source type* and *Way of determination*, as shown in the matrix in Table 6. There are three possible levels of uncertainty that go from Level 1, the most inaccurate (e.g., a datum produced by a technician assumption), to Level 3, the most accurate (e.g. a datum derived from a geographical database as an external

reference). An inconsistency may originate from specific combinations of *Source type* and *Way of determination* for which no level of uncertainty can be associated (e.g. a datum coming from a statistical database cannot be produced by a technician assumption).

Any further clarifying information can be provided in the *Notes* column.

4.1.4 Data applications

Finally, the *Data applications* section (Table 7) contains the information regarding a common use of each datum beyond the mere purpose of the EPC; three main applications are suggested, as follows:

- *Energy & Environmental Statistics*, which concern the use of the datum for statistical analysis in the energy and environmental fields.
- *Calibration or Validation*, which concern the use of the datum for energy model calibration or validation of calculation procedures.
- *Market surveys*, which concern the use of the datum in market analysis.

Any further data application type can be provided in the *Other* column.

Table 7. Overview of the *Data applications* section of the data collection sheet

<i>Data applications</i>			
Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
<i>True (✓) False (X)</i>	<i>True (✓) False (X)</i>	<i>True (✓) False (X)</i>	
<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>

4.2 Comparison tables

All the data gathered from the country partners through the data collection sheet were analysed, processed and compared, in order to identify similarities and differences concerning the EPC data availability and accuracy in the different countries or regions. In such a way, the context analysis on the EPC data is performed, in line with the objective of Task 1.3 of TIMEPAC.

Four comparison tables were produced, each one focusing on a specific research topic, such as:

- *EPC data availability.*
- *Data source and determination.*
- *Input accuracy.*
- *Overview of applications.*

Each topic delivers a specific information that originates from a different aggregation of the fields of the data collection sheet, as outlined in Figure 1 (Section 2.2).

4.2.1 EPC data availability

The comparison table *EPC data availability* concerns the information gathered about EPC contents with respect to the availability of the data and their presence in a specific database used at national/regional level.

An extract of the table is shown in Table 8. For each involved country, the table provides the general absence of the datum (grey cell), the presence of the datum in a given database (green cell) or the absence of the datum in a given database (red cell). The concerned databases are those considered in the *Contents* section of the data collection sheet.

This framework allows to have a clear picture of the EPC data availability in the different countries and to give suggestions regarding the data or indicators that should be made available or accessible in specific databases in the future.

Table 8. *EPC data availability* comparison table (extract)

	Name	Description	ITALY			CROATIA			CYPRUS		
			POLITO / EDIC / RP			EHP			CEA / CUT		
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC

The full content of the table is provided in Annex B (Table 26-Table 29).

By analysing the results, the main differences between countries are highlighted. The analysis of the partners' databases shows that the majority of the information is accessible in both the XML and the EPC documents, while the open-access database could be improved in some cases, like in Spain and Croatia. In Figure 2, the country percentages of availability of the data compared to the whole information considered in the data collection sheets are presented. As expected, there are discrepancies in the availability of the data from country to country, but a third of the examined information (i.e., the base list of EPC data) is common to all. Almost all partners inserted additional data, but mainly not common between them.

Figure 2. Percentage of the EPC data available compared to the whole information, by country

4.2.2 Data source and determination

The comparison table *Data source and determination* regards the origin and the way of determination of the data, as shown in Table 9. All the possible combinations of *Source type* and *Way of determination* that were assigned to the data in the collection sheets (*Data sources* section) are coloured in green, while the white cells mean that there is not any datum among those provided by the country partners that derives from those sources. Table 10 (extract) provides more detail: for each pairing of *Source type* and *Way of determination* identified by the green cells of Table 9, the list of the concerned data and the related country is given. The full content of Table 10 is in Annex B (Table 30-Table 31).

The objective of these tables is to provide general information regarding the sources and the ways deployed for the determination of the EPC data. Since a level of uncertainty in the input data determination can be associated to each couple of indicators (see Section 4.1.3), the analysis of the most frequent couples and their associated level of uncertainty allows to identify which data need an improvement of accuracy in their determination in the future. The number of occurrences of each couple and the associated level of uncertainty is shown in Figure 3 for the totality of analysed countries.

The analysis of the results shows that the majority of input information falls in a restricted group of combinations of *Source type* and *Way of determination* in which the most deployed *Source type* is “*technician defined*” and the most deployed *Way of determination* is “*external reference*”. Considering the whole group of countries, the highest number of occurrences for each combination of *Source type* and *Way of determination* are “*technician defined*” plus “*inspection*” and “*technician defined*” plus “*technician assumption*”. Since the input data related to these two combinations assume a mid-low level of accuracy, actions need to be taken in the future to increase the accuracy of the procedures for the input data determination. These inputs are mainly related to the building geometry, the thermo-physical properties of the envelope components, and the efficiencies of the technical building systems.

Table 9. Data source and determination comparison table

		WAY OF DETERMINATION						
		Inspection	Detailed calculation	Simplified calculation	Measurement / Monitoring	Technician assumption	External reference	NA
SOURCE TYPE	Cadastre database							
	Geographical database							
	Regional or national database							
	Statistical database							
	Survey on-site							
	Technician defined							
	Legislative or technical standard							
	Based on occupant interview							
	Existing energy report							
	Numerical assessment							
	Energy bills							
	NA							

Table 10. Data source and determination comparison table - detail of data by country (extract)

Cadastre database	Geographical database	Regional or national database	Statistical database	Survey on-site
External reference	External reference	External reference	External reference	Inspection
Geographical location - SLOVENIA	Geographical location - ITALY - SPAIN - AUSTRIA	Building typology - ITALY	Climatic region - CROATIA - SLOVENIA	Building address - CROATIA
Building address - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA	Building address - ITALY	Year of construction - ITALY		Building constructive typology - ITALY
Cadastre information - ITALY - CROATIA - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA		Year of last renovation - ITALY		Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA
Number of building units - ITALY - SLOVENIA		Climatic region - ITALY - CYPRUS - SPAIN		TBS energy carrier per energy service - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SPAIN - SLOVENIA
Building use - ITALY		TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service - AUSTRIA		TBS nominal power per energy service - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA
Information of building property - ITALY - CROATIA - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA				TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service - ITALY - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA
Year of construction - CROATIA - SLOVENIA				TBS year of installation per energy service - SLOVENIA

Figure 3. Number of occurrences of *Source type* and *Way of determination*, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - all countries

4.2.3 Input accuracy

The comparison table *Input accuracy* was developed from the *Level of uncertainty* (or *Suggested level of uncertainty*, if the former is lacking) information provided in the *Data quality* section of the data collection sheet. It is strictly related to *Data source and determination*, since the *Level of uncertainty* derives from the *Source type* and *Way of determination* items.

However, compared to the *Data source and determination* comparison table, the *Input accuracy* table provides information only on the input data (i.e., input data used for the building energy performance assessment) and not on the outputs, because the accuracy of the latter is also related to the calculation method used to perform the energy assessment.

An extract of the *Input accuracy* table is provided in Table 11. For each input data in the list, and for each country, the colour in the cell reveals the accuracy level, as follows: cells in orange indicate input data having low accuracy (i.e. highest level of uncertainty in the determination, or Level 1 in the data collection sheet), cells in yellow indicate input data having medium accuracy (i.e. medium level of uncertainty in the determination, or Level 2 in the data collection sheet), and cells in green indicate input data having high accuracy (i.e. lowest level of uncertainty in the determination, or Level 3 in the data collection sheet). The outputs and the intermediate results are in white cells as they are out of the scope of the analysis. The crossed out cells represent the unavailable data.

This comparison table grants an overview both on the differences of the input/output definition and on the differences of the level of uncertainty for the same data from country to country. This analysis gives the opportunity to better define the specific input data that need to be improved for what concerns the accuracy. For a given datum, the country showing the highest level of accuracy may provide the example to follow to increase the accuracy of the same information in another country.

The full content of the table is provided in Annex B (Table 32-Table 35).

The analysis of the results shows a good level of homogeneity in the collected data quality. Evidence of this is that the input/output definition and the determined input accuracy lead in almost all the cases to the same results, showing in that way similarities in the input data determination and calculation procedures in the considered countries.

Table 11. *Input accuracy* comparison table (extract)

Name	ITALY	CROATIA	CYPRUS
	POLITO / EDIC / RP	EIHP	CEA / CUT
Thermally conditioned floor area	Input	Input	Input
Thermally conditioned gross volume	Input	Input	
Compactness ratio	Intermediate result	Input	
Thermal envelope area	Input		Input
Opaque thermal envelope area	Input		Input
Transparent thermal envelope area	Input	Input	Input
Thermal envelope area per exposure	Intermediate result		Input
Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Intermediate result	Intermediate result	Intermediate result
Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Intermediate result		Intermediate result
Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Intermediate result		Intermediate result
Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Intermediate result	Intermediate result	Input
Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Input		Input
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit		Input	Input

4.2.4 Overview of applications

The last comparison table concerns an *Overview of applications*, and it is thus derived from the information provided by the country partners in the section *Data applications* of the data collection sheet. An extract of the table is provided in Table 12. The colours of the cells in the table mean that a datum is used for a given application, i.e., green, or is not used for a given application, i.e., orange. If the datum is not available, the cell is grey coloured.

The analysis of the data applications gives the opportunity to better understand and compare the exploitation fields of the data contained in the EPC for each country. This information is useful if linked to that delivered by the previous comparison table (*Input accuracy*). In fact, the identification of the most deployed data and the exploitation reasons can offer hints for the improvement of the input accuracy. The full content of the table is provided in Annex B (Table 36-Table 39).

The analysis of the results shows several similarities in the data application in the considered countries. The study of the collected information (Figure 4) reveals that the majority of data are deployed for energy and environmental statistics, while slightly more than 50% of data are applied

TIMEPAC D1.3 - Comparative analysis of EPC data

for calibration or validation procedures, and market surveys – apart from Austria, in which no data are used for market surveys. The percentage of data with no application is quite limited, except in Austria where this percentage is close to 30%.

Table 12. Overview of applications comparison table (extract)

Name	ITALY			CROATIA		
	POLITO / EDIC / RP			EIHP		
	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys
Assessed object	✓	X	X	✓	X	X
Application type	✓	X	X	✓	✓	X
Adopted simulation software	X	X	X			
Assessor's information	X	X	X	X	✓	X
EPC ID code	X	X	X	X	✓	X

Figure 4. Percentage of EPC data exploited in each country by type of application

5 Deficiencies and potential improvements on EPC data quality and contents

The present section provides a discussion on the outcomes of the comparison tables, outlining the main deficiencies on the current EPC data for each country/region, and delivering suggestions on improvements. It is structured into three main parts to address: (1) the quality of input data used for the building energy performance (EP) assessment, (2) the quality of outputs of the EP assessment methods that produce the indicators included in the EPC, and (3) the EPC data quality control systems in the concerned countries.

5.1 Input data for the building EP assessment

The present section is meant to answer to the following questions: *what are the deficiencies on input data about their quality (level of uncertainty)? Are any data missing? What are the related improvements needed (increase of quality for specific inputs, new information to be added in the EPC)?*

5.1.1 Austria

There is a big difference in the quality of input data for new buildings and existing buildings. While for new buildings the specific data can be found in the design documents needed for the building permit procedure, the data situation for existing buildings is usually poor. If plans are available, they are often not up to date, as changes are not tracked in the documents. To remedy this, default data are included in the calculation programmes, and there are also guidelines issued by the regional energy agencies giving advice how to determine input data for existing buildings. However, on-site inspection is not mandatory (Figure 5). The qualification of the expert issuing the EPC has a big impact on the quality of the input data.

Minimum requirements such as the heating demand are variable and depend on the surface-to-volume ratio of the building. This means for example, that the requirements for single-family houses are less strict than those ones for compact multi-storey residential buildings. The logic behind this is that a less favourable surface-to-volume ratio of a single family house requires greater insulation thicknesses (and more investment cost) than a multi-storey residential building with a favourable surface-to-volume ratio in order to achieve the same result in terms of heat transmission losses. This is important in terms of energy reduction targets, and it is a politically difficult issue because about half of all residential units are in single- and two-family houses.

Data about TBS is poorly represented in the EPC. There are funding programmes that have more ambitious requirements and also offer an expanded information base, such as the TBS database for renewable energy systems, heat pumps and ventilation systems in the province of Salzburg. This is technical information useful for engineers, but less important for building owners and tenants. Regarding building owners and tenants, the main challenge is that consumers do not understand the technical indicators of the EPC: which of the many indicators can be translated into energy cost? Is the number good or bad? If the number is good, what is the best possible value and how much would the additional cost be to achieve it? If the number is bad, what are the consequences (e.g., in terms of CO₂ emissions and phase out fossil systems)? Cost data would be useful, but those responsible are reluctant to provide them because of the wide range of possible variations.

The range of possible input data affects the assessment result, which is particularly important if the building performance is between two EPC scale levels, e.g., B or C. In such a case, the input data could be set to achieve the better result, and this possibility should be avoided.

The definition of the reference area (conditioned floor area) must be clear as this is crucial for the resulting indicators: for example, if the basement is heated, is it included or not? It is not classified as “useful area”, and there are different views how to deal with it. With regard to the real estate

sector, better alignment is needed to avoid misunderstandings and errors. For example, the real estate sector is not familiar with “conditioned gross floor area”, they use “gross floor area”. Actually, the “conditioned gross floor area” can be a source of errors.

In summary, the quality of input data needs to be improved to ensure that it is correct and building specific, and in this regard, quality of on-site visits and the qualification of the responsible staff are crucial. Information on technical building systems has been gaining importance due to the EU decarbonisation targets. In general, the EPC contains valuable information for engineers, consumers, and the real estate sector. However, the information must be presented in a user-specific way to maximise its effectiveness.

Figure 5. Number of occurrences of *Source type* and *Way of determination*, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Austria

5.1.2 Croatia

The EPC is a document mainly addressed to the end-user. However, the main EPC data concern the technical nature of the energy performance indicators. Therefore, without adequate end-user knowledge to understand the indicators, the information remains relatively unexploitable.

The analysis of the input availability in the EPC showed a lot of missing data, in particular envelope and windows areas, transmittance values and SRI indicators. Most of this information is already accessible in the software, and it can be included in the XML output file in the future. An update of the database is in development and some issues will be addressed.

Regarding the input accuracy, in analogy with the comparative results presented in Section 4.2.2 and showed in Figure 6 for Croatia, the major issues are related to technician inspections. So, it is crucial to promote and upgrade current educational programs, as well as periodic controls of issued EPCs. Controls in Croatia showed that around 40% of issued EPCs that have been chosen for control process, are not compliant with requirements of legislation and/or defined energy certification process. This does not mean that 40% of all EPCs are void and incorrect, as mostly suspicious EPCs are controlled (the ones that have some calculation results that are outliers).

Figure 6. Number of occurrences of *Source type* and *Way of determination*, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Croatia

5.1.3 Cyprus

Many of the EPC certification weaknesses may occur because of the incorrect imported data or the wrong methodology of calculation from the SBEM software (Figures 7, 8, and 9). Considering that the data for the procedure are directly connected to the results, any mistake can affect the accuracy of the certification. Some of the input information must be calculated from the user and, as a result, the possibility of a human error in the process increases.

Some of the important values, such as U-value, are calculated by the energy expert instead by means of an automatic calculation system. This method may increase the human error. Additionally, the methodology for the calculation of some parameters is obsolete and, as a result, the quality of the certification decreases. One of those inaccurate input methods concerns the photovoltaic system of the building. In case of an existing or a suggested system, the installed power and the annual production is calculated based on the covered area and not based on the actual installed power. For instance, on 18 m² area few years ago the maximum installed power was 2.5 kW - 3.0 kW, but today covering the same area the installed power can be 4.8 kW - 5.3 kW.

Figure 7. Input data to model the photovoltaic system in SBEM (SBEM, 2014) (1)

One of the weakest points during the import procedure is the incomplete information for the frames and masonry that can be entered in the software. According to the EPC certified experts, the 2D representation of the building deprives the user to import all the information.

Figure 8. Input data to model the photovoltaic system in SBEM (SBEM, 2014) (2)

There are many improvements that can be applied to the EPC procedure and the implementation of the suggestions to improve the quality and the purpose of the certification.

A major upgrade of the software is needed in many levels such as:

- The interface must become friendlier to the user.
- Improvement of the troubleshooting (Online chat, FQ&A, etc.).
- Adding of libraries for the materials including also previously used technologies.
- Possibility to enter in a 3D environment the details of the elements on the building instead of the existing 2D representation.

Figure 9. Interface of SBEM (SBEM, 2014)

In conclusion, in Cyprus the input data for the EPC are not very accurate and the procedure in general is static. Many calculations are oversimplified with many assumptions and standardised inputs for systems. As a result, the combination of all the above aspects increases the level of uncertainty and degrades the importance of the EPC.

Regarding the input accuracy, in analogy with the comparative results presented in Section 4.2.2 and showed in Figure 10 for Cyprus, the major issues are related to technician inspections. In order to rise the accuracy, an improvement of the awareness of the inspectors should be pursued, as well as the definition of more stringent external control procedures.

Figure 10. Number of occurrences of Source type and Way of determination, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Cyprus

5.1.4 Italy

The analysis of the input data availability in the Italian EPC showed very few missing data; in particular, the information regarding the limit values used for the verification of the calculated EP indicators is not available, while of course it is deployed for the verification procedure. This information is already accessible in the software, and it should be included in the XML output file in the future. In addition, a deficiency in the input data relates to the lack of interoperability between different regional or national databases. This leads to a lack of control by the IT system in the compilation of data by the energy assessors.

In the Italian EPC, the data regarding thermo-physical properties of layers of the building envelope components are not available. To carry out an energy certification, the on-site inspection is mandatory. However, for the energy performance assessment of existing buildings and in absence of clear information about materials that compose the stratigraphy, the technical standard UNI/TR 11552 (UNI, 2014), which provides an abacus of the typical opaque building envelope components classified by the period of construction and the region of origin, can be deployed. Moreover, the consultation of the territorial cadastre database allows to obtain the land/cadastre parcel to insert in the identification data section of the EPC schema. DPR 74/2013 (Italian Republic, 2013) established that Regions and Autonomous Provinces have to set up a territorial register of thermal technical building systems. More than 70% of the Italian Regions and Autonomous Provinces have the thermal technical building systems database (ENEA & CTI, 2021) that uniquely established the identification number and the characteristics of the heat generators. Moreover, in Piemonte the energy performance of buildings information system (SIPEE) is available, where private citizens and energy assessors can freely access to the information contained in the stored EPCs. This database represents a source of information especially for the technician in charge. The upload of the energy certificate in the regional database is a mandatory requirement to validate the document.

Concerning other missing data in the Italian EPC, no suggestions are made to raise awareness of responsible energy consumption among landlords or tenants. Additionally, state funding mechanism information could be introduced to raise end-user consciousness about the renovation possibility of the building envelope and/or the technical building systems.

Regarding the input accuracy, in analogy with the comparative results presented in Section 4.2.2 and showed in Figure 11 for Italy (Piemonte region), the major issues are related to technician inspections. In order to rise the accuracy, an improvement of the awareness of the inspectors should be pursued, as well as the definition of more stringent external control procedures.

Figure 11. Number of occurrences of Source type and Way of determination, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Italy

5.1.5 Slovenia

The EPC in Slovenia is considered as a technical document, although it is mainly addressed to the general public. Without adequate knowledge from the end-user, the essential information of the EPC is unclear. This results in general in neglecting the EPC content and production just for the sake of legislation. The EPCs key essential information is based on valid input data, since the calculation must be based on either building documentation or measured energy consumption. The software for EPC issuing is connected to the national Register of Real Estates which enables quality assurance control and thus improves its quality.

Few missing data are shown in particular in the analysis of the input availability: the information regarding the nZEB indicators that should be already integrated in the EPC. This EPC upgrade is missing and is depending on the acceptance of a new Rule of energy efficiency in buildings, which is going to define those indicators on the level of: energy need, share of RES and non-renewable primary energy. As it stands, the EPC is showing the nZEB level from the Action plan for nZEB in Slovenia from 2015.

Further suggestions are made in order to raise awareness of energy use in buildings among tenants/building owners. The new information in the EPC should be more insightful and present information on possible improvements of the building’s energy efficiency (building envelope and/or the technical building system) from the economic aspect as well and furthermore, the standard

calculated EPC should present a qualitative information on the energy consumption in economic terms as well. Additionally, to raise end-user consciousness about the renovation possibility, funding mechanism information could be introduced in the EPC schema.

Regarding the input accuracy, in analogy with the comparative results presented in Section 4.2.2 and shown in Figure 12 for Slovenia, the major issues are related to technician inspections. In order to rise the accuracy, an improvement of the awareness of the inspectors should be pursued, as well as the definition of more stringent external control procedures.

Figure 12. Number of occurrences of Source type and Way of determination, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Slovenia

5.1.6 Spain

There are different types of input data in the energy certification program in Spain, according to which the degree of uncertainty (Figure 13) varies:

- **Administrative data:** address, cadastre, personal data of the property and the person who signs the energy certificate.
- **Data according to regulations:** this is the case for the climate zone, the demand for domestic hot water or ventilation. The latter is a very sensitive fact in energy certificates.
- **Data by project,** if this information is available: definition of enclosures and facilities.
- **Default data:** if the project is not available, the transmittance of the enclosures and the performance of the facilities are defined according to the year of construction, assuming that the current regulations are complied with. These are conservative data.
- **Data according to visual inspection:** for example, finishing of façades, type of glass of the windows...

In all cases, errors are detected by the persons involved in the certification, control or inspection, and are corrected, in Catalonia, with a specific amendment procedure (ICAEN, 2022). Mistakes can be very varied: type of building, incorrect surface, error in the address of the building, etc.

In the register of energy certificates from Catalonia, some data is beginning to be asked regarding the actual consumption of buildings and the type of appliances. This is voluntary and approximate data, therefore not everyone has this information.

A significant improvement in the quality of energy certificates can come from rethinking the requirements to be certified by technical staff. According to Royal Decree 390/2021 (Government of Spain, 2021), there must be a rethink in the conditions of December 3, 2022. Now the requirement is to have a degree in architecture, technical architecture, engineering or technical engineering. It remains to be seen what the requirements are, perhaps to do some specific course.

Figure 13. Number of occurrences of Source type and Way of determination, and associated level of uncertainty of input data (1-Lowest accuracy, 2-Medium accuracy, 3-Highest accuracy) - Spain

5.2 EP assessment methods and related outputs

The quality of the EPC data concerns not only the input data used to assess the building energy performance (Section 5.1), but also the calculation methods and tools that provide the outputs (EP indicators in the EPC). A short overview of the current assessment methods of the building energy performance is provided in the present section as to address the accuracy of the calculation outputs. This section is meant to answer to the following questions: *Is an increase of accuracy needed? What are the major issues? What new outputs/indicators should be included in the EPC?*

5.2.1 Austria

The assessment methods are specified by OIB Guideline 6 (OIB, 2019) with references to more detailed Austrian standards which were developed before CEN standards were available. For existing buildings, a simplified assessment procedure can be applied, based on mainly default data. With regard to new buildings, the detailed calculation method also contains default data which can be replaced by specific data. There are five approved calculation programmes available on the market, with differing data input requirements.

The type of calculation must be specified in the technical annex of the EPC. Although the technical annex is part of the EPC, in practice it is not always given to the building owner or tenant, and if it is, the building owner or tenant is usually not able to interpret this information due to lack of knowledge. There has been a long discussion about more accurate (building specific) EPCs versus cost of EPCs. EPCs must be cheap and are done to comply with the law, but are not acknowledged by the real estate industry as a valuable document. Usually, owners and tenants are only familiar with the scale, meaning green represents best performance and red represents worst performance. There is the opinion, that good default values can keep cost low and provide a sufficient level of accuracy. However, recommendations for improving the energy performance of the building will be only general. There is a discussion if on-site inspection done for the EPC can be as detailed as an investment grade energy audit according to Energy Efficiency Directive. Currently, an investment grade energy audit will be necessary to make specific recommendations for renovation measures and provide information about investment cost and savings. Thus, the need for an increase in accuracy depends on how EPC data should be used.

Information about technical building systems should be improved, also in the light of renewable energy systems and zero greenhouse gas emission targets. Information about indoor climate, indoor air quality, and noise levels should also be shown, as this can be either improved or worsened as a consequence of implementing or not implementing energy saving measures.

5.2.2 Croatia

The calculation method of the building energy performance in force in Croatia is provided by the series of EU and German standards, mainly EN ISO 13790 (CEN, 2008), EN 15316 (CEN, 2017a), DIN V 18599 series (DIN, 2018). To the purpose of determining the energy rating for the building EPC, a monthly quasi-steady-state calculation method of the building energy needs is applied, in compliance with the EN ISO 13790 (CEN, 2008) technical standard. Additionally, in the last 3 years calculation of primary energy need has been implemented, taking into account technical building systems. The adoption of fully dynamic or simplified dynamic methods, introduced by the EN ISO 52016-1 (CEN, 2017b), to carry out the certification process, does not necessarily guarantee an increase in the accuracy of the output data calculation, especially if the energy assessor is unqualified. Maybe, for certain intended uses or particularly complex buildings, the adoption of dynamic calculation models may be recommended, even though limiting the price increase for the EPC issue would have to be addressed. Currently, in Croatia, the reference building approach is discussed where the audited building is compared to a baseline building with the same geometrical data, defined thermal characteristics and defined technical systems.

The *Smart Readiness Indicator* (SRI) represents a new crucial indicator to be included in the Croatian EPC schema aimed at broadening the technological development of BACS (Building, Automation and Control Systems), and also at assessing their impact in buildings.

5.2.3 Cyprus

The calculation method of the building energy performance in force in Cyprus falls under the EU directive 2002/91/EC on the energy performance of buildings (European Parliament, 2002).

For the issuance of an EPC, the building owner or their representative appoints the EPC Qualified Expert by co-signing the relevant form in Annex 3 of the relevant regulations (Cyprus Republic, 2009 and Cyprus Republic, 2014).

The assessment method used widely in Cyprus at the moment is iSBEMcy software. The software is available free of charge from the Energy Office of Cyprus for the calculation of building energy performance and the issue of an EPC, however only EPC Qualified Experts (i.e., registered by the Energy Agency in the Register of EPC Qualified Experts for a defined category or categories of buildings) are eligible to issue Building Energy Performance Certificates.

The EPC quality is strongly influenced by the accuracy of the inputs and thus the accuracy of its results, therefore the assessment methodology including their standardized inputs are key to

achieve quality information. These become critical for existing buildings, which are the ones that are most energy inefficient in the sector. Several studies carried out in the EU have reported inferior energy savings than expected in retrofit projects as well differences between assumed indoor temperatures and actually used ones. Irrespective of the gap between simulation and actual energy saved, the EPC calculations are not comparable with the actual performance due to the use of standardised conditions and a number of loads that are not included in the energy performance calculations. These might be appropriate for the purposes of comparing the energy performance of buildings. However, when it comes to set energy efficiency recommendations for renovation purposes, standardised procedure might not be adequate, since the estimation of the energy savings and the accuracy of the measures for the renovation requires an analysis based on real energy consumption.

In that context, the EPC (Figure 14) could have two versions: a more detailed/accurate one for constructors and professionals and a user-friendly version for owners with minimum understanding of technical context. For the EPC report to be more accurate, some of the indicators that could be included are: the year of construction or last renovation of the building, the year of installation of generator per energy service, overall non-renewable energy performance indicators. For the simplified version, in the recommendations section the CO₂ emissions saved could be shown in correspondence with real examples that are easily interpreted. Likewise, energy classes in this version should be further explained - what does it mean for my building to have a C, D class etc.

ΣΥΣΤΑΣΕΙΣ

ΣΥΣΤΑΣΕΙΣ

Στοιχεία ειδικευμένου εμπειρογνώμονα		Details of registered expert	
Όνομα Ειδικευμένου Εμπειρογνώμονα	Γεωργίου Γεωργίου	Name	
Αρ. Ειδικευμένου Εμπειρογνώμονα	ΑΒΧΧ100054	Unique number of registered expert	
Όνομα Εργοδότη/Εταιρείας	Τεχνολογικό Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου	Name of employer / company	
Διεύθυνση Εργασίας	Αθηνών και Νίκου Ειούτα 2ος Όροφος	Address	
Ταχ.Κωδ.	3040	Post code	
Επαρχία	Λεμεσός	Province	
Τηλ: 25002100	Email: ggeorgio@techn.ac.cy	Phone and Email	

Στοιχεία Κτιρίου		Details of building	
Όνομα έργου	Κτήριο Λαϊκής	Name of building / project	
Διεύθυνση	Αθηνών και Νίκου Ειούτα 2ος Όροφος	Address	
Δήμος/Κοινότητα	Λεμεσός	Region	
Ταχ.Κωδ.	3040	Post code	
Επαρχία	Λεμεσός	Province	
Φ/Σχ 54/580504	Unique number of land of building	Τμήμα 2 Section	Τεμάχιο 492 Fragment
Πιστοποίηση κτιρίου	Μετά την κατασκευή	Type of Certification (i.e: before or after building was built)	
Τύπος κτιρίου	ΓΡΑΦΕΙΟ	Type of building (i.e: office, school, residential building...)	
Οφέλιμο εμβαδό δαπέδου (m ²)	2332,07	Floor area of project	
Κλιματικό περιβάλλον	Κλιματιζόμενο	Built environment (i.e: air-conditioned)	

Figure 14. Sample of a section of an EPC report for Cyprus

5.2.4 Italy

The calculation method of the building energy performance in force in Italy is provided by the Italian UNI/TS 11300 series (UNI, 2010-2019) of technical specifications. To the purpose of determining the energy rating for the building EPC, a monthly quasi-steady-state calculation method of the building energy needs is applied, in compliance with the EN ISO 13790 (CEN, 2008) technical standard. Whereas the EP assessment method is simple, it loses in the output accuracy, which could be instead increased by applying a dynamic energy model but with a consequent increase in complexity.

At the European level, a new calculation methodology is being discussed to harmonize EPCs across Member States. Although the simplified dynamic hourly calculation, recently introduced by EN ISO 52016-1 (CEN, 2017b) that superseded EN ISO 13790 (CEN, 2008), would provide a more robust methodology, this would not necessarily lead to better results if applied incorrectly or by unqualified energy assessors. Maybe, the adoption of dynamic calculation models may be mandatory for certain intended uses or for particularly complex buildings, with a possible increase of the prices for the EPC issue. In addition, new energy models should be implemented as to assess the new technologies now available in the market (e.g., PCM components, adaptive facades, cool roofs, etc.).

In Italy, the simplified-calculation procedure to carry out an EPC is only applicable to residential existing buildings or building units with a useful floor area less or equal to 200 m². Moreover, the Italian Thermotechnical Committee (CTI) carries out a verification activity of commercial software and tools for the energy performance assessment of buildings. Nineteen software programs have been validated in Italy to calculate the energy performance of buildings.

The non-renewable overall energy performance indicator ($EP_{gl;nren}$) determines the energy rating of the building or building unit. However, $EP_{gl;nren}$ does not necessarily represent the effective consumption or environmental impact of the building, but only the non-renewable primary energy delivered to the technical building systems. For instance, the exploitation of biomasses could imply a high level of the renewable overall energy performance indicator ($EP_{gl;ren}$), but the combustion of the cited energy carrier can have a considerable environmental impact. Therefore, to rate a building or a building unit, an indicator that considers in a holistic way the exploitation of renewable sources, building consumption, and the quantification of the GHG emitted in the atmosphere must be provided in the next-generation EPCs.

The qualification of the energy assessors is the main aspect that affects the reliability of the EPC data quality. In Italy, technicians belonging to the professional association are enabled to carry out an EPC. Otherwise, it is mandatory to pass an examination.

As concerns new indicators to be included in the EPC, a relevant information not yet available in Italy regards the *Smart Readiness Indicator* (SRI); in order to broaden the technological development of the BACS (Building, Automation and Control Systems), and also to assess their impact in buildings, it is of extreme importance to include this parameter both in the calculation procedure and in the EPC schema.

5.2.5 Slovenia

The calculation method of the building energy performance in force in Slovenia is provided by the EN ISO 13790 (CEN, 2008), based on the Rules of energy efficiency and its technical guideline. For the energy class calculation, a monthly quasi-steady-state calculation method of the building energy needs is applied, in compliance with the EN ISO 13790 (CEN, 2008) technical standard. Whereas the EP assessment method is simple, it loses in the output accuracy, which could be instead increased by applying a dynamic energy model but with a consequent increase in complexity. Within the upgraded Rules of energy efficiency (to be adopted in 2022), the dynamic calculation method will be prescribed for large complex buildings from the EP aspect.

The main issue when dealing with dynamic EP methods relate to (i) suitable software and (2) educated EPC makers. Dynamic EP methods are not widely used in Slovenia, which can also be said for most European countries. They are mainly research based and before wider use for EPC production, extensive trainings should be executed.

New indicators/information that have to be included in the upgraded EPC can be summarized in groups: (1) calculation method, (2) SRI indicators, (3) BACS indicators, (4) economically justifiable energy renovation and (5) energy consumption from the economic aspect.

5.2.6 Spain

In Spain, it is mandatory to use one of the seven programs recognized by the state to make the energy certificate of buildings. These are classified into two groups:

- General tools (there are four). A three-dimensional simulation of the building is performed. One of the tools, CYPETHERM, uses BIM.
- Simplified tools (there are three). Enclosure surfaces are defined and the tool simplifies the building into a box.

The general tools, which perform the energy simulation, are more accurate. Simplified tools, on the other hand, are more agile and are used in most certificates, especially in existing buildings.

There is a big difference between whether or not there is a project of the building. Whether it is new construction or refurbishment, there is a project, and therefore a lot of information to make a very careful energy certificate. In this case, if a BIM tool is used, the contradictions between the project and the energy certificate, which duplicate the information, are reduced.

On the other hand, if it is an existing building, most of the time the information collected in the visual inspection of the building (surfaces, enclosures, installations ...) is available. For the information available, it is proportional to be able to use a simplified tool.

It would be interesting to include in the EPC the actual energy consumed (complementary to the calculated energy). It would also be important to include embedded energy in the materials, as well as the energy performance certificate to be related to the building renovation passport (according to the draft of the new building energy efficiency directive, in 2024, we will have a common framework to be able to develop this document).

Other environmental impacts of buildings should be related to the energy performance certificate. The European directive provides that the common Level(s) framework should be applied to the environmental assessment of buildings.

5.3 Current approaches for data quality control

The present section is meant to answer to the following questions: *Are there any certification tools / protocols to validate data in the EPC (e.g., used by the certification bodies who verify the EPC reliability)? Are there any procedures, methods, instruments that detect essential data quality issues? What are the main limits that prevent broader application of EPC data in the country?*

5.3.1 Austria

The assessment methods are specified by OIB Guideline 6 (OIB, 2019) with references to more detailed Austrian standards including validation examples, which are used to prove the reliability of EPC calculation programs.

In the calculation programs, there are some plausibility checks carried out during data entry. Another automatic check is performed during uploading the EPC calculation and results XML to the EPC database. There is an informal exchange of information between the calculation software companies, the competent authority and the company programming the EPC database to identify factors affecting the quality of EPCs and to implement improvements.

There is the independent control system installed with the competent authority at regional level according to EPBD Article 18 (European Parliament, 2010), meaning that a sample of EPCs is checked in more detail. At the beginning of EPBD implementation and before implementing the independent control system, many EPCs were recalculated by the responsible authority, and direct feedback was provided to EPC experts with the requirement for re-submission. There is no sanction for bad performance of EPC experts. A faulty EPC can be brought to court under civil law, but this is very rare.

Currently, EPC data are not publicly accessible. There is an issue with personal data protection, because the building address is classified as suitable to identify a person. Nevertheless, this problem could be solved by aggregation of data to a level which is still meaningful for users and at the same time complies with personal data protection rules. However, there are three main reasons why this effort has not been undertaken so far:

- The EPBD, the recast and the amendment resulted in an adaptation of the OIB Guideline 6 (OIB, 2019) and thus of the EPC (2007, 2011, 2015, 2019); currently 3 valid versions are on the market due to the validity period of 10 years, and this would cause confusion.
- There are quality problems with EPCs issued for existing buildings outside of a funding scheme, which is why the data are considered unreliable.
- The building stock is not well covered by EPCs because many buildings have been never rented or sold, or under major renovation.

5.3.2 Croatia

Data validation and quality controls of EPCs are mandatory. Expert supervision of EPCs and inspection reports are carried out by the Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets. According to the Article 40 of Building Act (Croatian Republic, 2013), the Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets is obliged to supervise and verify EPCs. In more detail, according to Article 16 of the Ordinance on the control of the energy certificate of the building and the report on the regular inspection of the heating system and the cooling or air conditioning system in the building (Croatian Republic, 2015), the Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets is obliged to supervise and verify at least a statistically significant share of annually issued EPCs and energy audit reports. Annual expert supervision includes verification of building data, input data and results presented on EPCs, energy audit reports and energy efficiency recommendations. Quality control is provided by licenced institutions and companies. The report on quality control can annul a specific EPC, and if there are three invalid EPCs of the same energy performance certifier this leads to cancelation of licence to perform energy audits and EPCs. Energy Institute Hrvoje Požar is licensed for conducting quality controls. EPCs can be annulled on the following basis:

- Calculated annual energy need for heating per useful floor area for the reference climatic data or calculated annual primary energy per useful floor area for the reference climatic data differ more than 30% from the correct value.
- Any of the two energy efficiency classes printed on the EPC are different from the class obtained in quality control.
- Energy efficiency measures are not calculated and defined as described in the Methodology (Croatian Republic, 2021).
- Energy audit report is not composed according to requirements described in the Methodology.

Around 30 EPCs are validated on a monthly basis. During quality control mostly output data are validated, but in extreme cases input data are also checked (when the data are deemed inconsistent and unrealistic). No on-site check is implemented, but it can be done during quality control process.

5.3.3 Cyprus

The Energy Service of the Ministry of Energy, Commerce and Industry are responsible for the issuance and validation of the EPCs in the Republic of Cyprus. Each EPC has a unique certificate registration number on the top left-hand side of the first page. Verification of the authenticity of the EPC could be carried online through the Ministry's website. Each report has a 10-year validity period and random on-site checks could be performed by the Energy Service. However, there are no external certification bodies who check the EPC reliability and the random checks are rarely performed, allowing a flexibility to deceive the system.

In Cyprus we notice that in cases where EPCs are not required (selling/buying a house, renting a flat etc.), they are not issued. This might occur because of the lack of initiatives for end-users to issue an EPC and the limited understanding of why an EPC is important, other than the legal requirement. As a result of the limited application of EPCs in Cyprus, a public database creation is currently particularly challenging.

5.3.4 Italy

The Environmental Regional Agency (ARPA) is in charge of the control on the issued EPCs. This activity is performed twofold, in the first instance with a documentary check and then with onsite inspections.

The documentary check is implemented on a sample of 2% of the EPCs delivered by professionals each year (Italian Republic, 2015). The check aims at verifying that the EPC data are reliable on the basis of benchmarking indicators. For instance, the following parameters are taken into account:

- Coherence of the geometry of the building/flat (i.e., ratio between volume and surface).
- Average yield of the heating system.
- Administrative data related to the building and the issuing of the EPC.
- Consistency of energy data (i.e., performance index according to the year of construction, etc.).

However, the check is not intended to validate the EPC, but to spot inconsistencies and unrealistic data. DPR 74/2013 (Italian Republic, 2013) established three different levels to verify the quality of the EPCs transmitted to the Regional or Autonomous Provinces databases. Random controls are prioritized towards the most efficient energy ratings, and include:

- Type A check that provides the documentary assessment and the compliance with the energy performance calculation procedures.
- Type B control activity based on the coherence and adequacy of the quality of the data stored in the EPCs.
- Type C check that provides on-site inspection.

However, only nine Italian Regions and Autonomous Provinces declare the adoption of the control protocol (ENEA & CTI, 2021) especially focused on the first two levels: type A and type B. The Italian D. Lgs. 192/2005 (Italian Republic, 2005) states administrative penalty between 700 and 4.200 euros for non-compliant EPCs with current legislation.

The on-site check is implemented on the basis of citizens/tenants complaints. The inspection in this case checks that the EPC is coherent with the real conditions of the building. In case of discrepancies a fine is applied and the EPC must be reissued.

The EPC system is broadly applied in Italy, as it is compulsory by law. The problem of quality is related to several issues, such as:

- The qualification of the professionals (no specific skill must be proven before delivering EPCs).
- The fact that the EPC is compulsory in case of sales and rents brings the homeowners to go for a best effort solution. The prices on the market are, thus, very low with very low quality and in several cases the EPC is not reliable.
- The validating procedures are regional based and they are not harmonised at national level.

5.3.5 Slovenia

The Ministry of Infrastructure and an external contractor are in charge of the control on the issued EPCs. The process for data quality control is performed twofold, in the first instance when issuing an EPC with cross-checking with national databases and then with documentary check.

The documentary check is implemented on a statistically relevant sample of the EPCs delivered by professionals each year. The check aims at verifying that the EPC data is reliable on the basis of benchmarking indicators. For instance, the following parameters are taken into account:

- Coherence of the geometry of the building/flat.
- Deviation of the energy indicators consistency from energy consumption data.

5.3.6 Spain

In Spain, energy certification regulations are identical throughout the state. In contrast, every region has its register.

In the case of Catalonia, we have a configurable alarm system to be able to detect inconsistencies in the data of the energy certificates (for example, incongruous transmittances, very high performance of the facilities...). In addition, the inspection is carried out on 1% of the energy performance certificates submitted.

These alarms are incorporated into the registration application forms, consequently, at the time of presenting the certificate, two types of messages can be displayed:

- Error: Does not allow to present the certificate until it is corrected (these are errors that affect the rating). For example, if the certificate states that it is tertiary and the form states that it is a dwelling.
- Warning: It is recommended to review certain data to improve the quality of the certificate (for example, the performance of a heat pump).

The new regulations (Government of Spain, 2021) extend the cases in which the energy performance certificate must be issued. Until now it was for new construction, buildings for sale or rent and administration buildings of more than 250 m². From June 3, 2022, the certificate must also be made in certain renovations, if the technical inspection of the building is done, and for buildings of certain uses of more than 500 m² (teaching, administrative, public residential...).

6 Relation to other tasks

The outcomes of the comparison tables and the aspects outlined in Section 5 allow to draw recommendations to develop the subsequent phase of the TIMEPAC project. The results of the present deliverable will inform the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs) that are aimed at developing and delivering new methods to implement enhanced EPC schemas in WP2.

The relationship between each comparison table and the TDSs is summarized in Figure 15. In fact, the outcomes of the comparison tables are meant to provide some key-questions that will be answered in the TDSs, through the delivery of specific methods, indicators, schemas, etc.

Figure 15. Relationship between the outcomes of the comparison tables and the objectives of the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs) of TIMEPAC

More specifically, the deficiencies highlighted by the involved countries/regions on the EPC data analysis will be overcome in WP2 by developing the Transversal Deployment Scenarios. In Table 13, a list of recommendations coming from the outcomes of Task 1.3 is provided, as well as the related TDSs that will be informed.

Table 13. Recommendations based on outcomes of Task 1.3 and related TDSs (WP2)

Recommendations based on outcomes of Task 1.3	TDS	Task of WP2
Integration of BIM and EPC to increase building model accuracy	TDS 1	Task 2.1
Interoperability between different databases to reduce input data uncertainty	TDS 1	Task 2.1
More accurate calculation models of the building EP assessment	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Economic indicators related to energy efficiency measures and operational data (e.g., annual energy costs) in the EPC	TDS 2	Task 2.2

TIMEPAC D1.3 - Relation to other tasks

Recommendations based on outcomes of Task 1.3	TDS	Task of WP2
Funding mechanisms included in the EPC as to raise end-user awareness about energy refurbishment actions	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Actual energy consumption and environmental indicators (e.g., GHG emissions) in the EPC	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Nearly zero-energy building (NZEB) indicators in the EPC	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) indicators in the EPC	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Building Automation and Control Systems (BACS) information in the EPC	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Technical indicators more understandable by final-users	TDS 2	Task 2.2
Integration of Building Renovation Passport (BRP) and EPC	TDS 3	Task 2.3
Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) in the EPC	TDS 4	Task 2.4
Identification of factors that affect the quality of EPC	TDS 5	Task 2.5
Validity check and controls on input data, above all for that information coming from technician inspection and assumption	TDS 5	Task 2.5

7 Conclusions

The research activity carried out in Task 1.3 (WP1) of TIMEPAC analysed the current situation of EPC data. The adopted approach is innovative because recent EPC data quality surveys usually focus only on selected data accuracy and consistency issues, which do not cover the full range from input data to output data and all the necessary levels of validation, and thus do not reveal those essential data quality issues that prevent a broader application of the EPC data.

A new instrument to collect the necessary information in the participating countries/regions, namely the data collection sheet, was developed. By processing the information of the data collection sheets, some comparison tables were delivered. Deficiencies in the current EPC data availability and quality were outlined and specific recommendations to be addressed in the Transversal Deployment Scenarios of TIMEPAC (WP2) are drawn. The final aim is to improve the EPC data and, generally, to make progress in the existing energy certification processes, moving from a single and static certification to a holistic and dynamic approach. The analysis underpins the relevance of TIMEPAC for investigating the BIM approach to address the identified deficiencies.

The analysis highlighted how the data quality issue strongly affects the EPC reliability, which is commonly verified by the certification and validation bodies in each country. The accuracy of EPC data is a necessary condition to guide public decision-making to renovate the most energy-intensive building stock, to assess the fuel poverty, and to progressively evaluate the refurbishment of the building stock following the issue of the fiscal incentives. The EPC data quality mainly depends on three factors: the validity of input data, the EP calculation methodology and applied tools, and the assessor's qualification. However, the competence of the expert in charge of carrying out the EPC has the greatest influence on the final result.

The results on the comparison of data sources, along with the results on the level of uncertainty, showed the main differences in the data origin and accuracy, and underlined the main fields in which an accuracy improvement should be performed. Most of data come from technicians' assessments and assumptions, thus a more efficient control system on input data should be carried out to guarantee the accuracy in the inputs. Plausibility intervals may be included in the calculation software for specific input data. In addition, the interoperability of the data between different regional or national databases improves the reliability of the EPC information, as well as the exploitation of BIM for the EPC generation.

In addition of the issue of data quality, it is necessary to include more indicators in the EPCs (e.g., smart readiness indicators, sustainability indicators, economic indicators, etc.) and to increase the availability of EPC data from different databases. For the former, the indicators can be used to assess the performance of new technologies (e.g. advanced and smart building components), to take into account the building management by the user, to include cost-effective energy efficiency measures, to address environmental impacts, etc. In this way, the application fields of the EPC can be enlarged as it can really become an effective instrument for the achievement of the decarbonisation of the building stock.

As regards to data availability in the EPC, the full dataset is not available in the analysed countries (see Annex A - Data collection sheets of each participating country). Since most of the data derive from software calculations, it should be possible to modify the calculation procedure in order to homologate the availability of data. Given that some of these data are not currently deployed for the purpose of the EPC, it can be a reasonable approach to collect them only in the XML database, in order to store the whole information, but at the same time to avoid an information overload in the EPC schemas. The analysis of the availability in the single databases underlined, in some cases, the absence of data in open databases. Further study should establish the possibility of storing information in open databases - while taking into account privacy issues - in order to broaden the possibility of using data.

As concerns the EP calculation procedures, improved assessment methods should be set up, as to guarantee, at the same time, the simplicity of the calculation and the accuracy of the numerical

model. The assessors would take advantage from the simplicity of the calculation, and the costs for the final user would not increase. At the same time, the accuracy of the numerical model would reduce the uncertainty of the output and increase the reliability of the EPC indicators.

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Annexes

Annex A – Data collection sheets of each participating country

Data collection sheet - Austria (Province of Salzburg)

Table 14. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Austria)

	Contents						Data sources			Data quality			Data applications								
	Name	Description	Content database			Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other		
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database															Availability of the content in the EPC scheme	True (-) / False (X) (optional)
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list- (Look at caption)>	<Choice from list- (Look at caption)>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
EPC information on the assessed object (not an assessor)	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative							✓	X	X	Policy making, applicable also for the rows below			
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative							✓	X	X				
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative							X	X	X				
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative							X	X	X				
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative							X	X	X				
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	Yes	✓	X	X	Geographical information	Qualitative	Input	Not available in current EPC scheme; should be included; would be input	Geographical database	External reference		Level 3				X	X	Policy making, applicable also for the rows below	
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geographical information	Qualitative	Input	Information is available but not included in the current EPC scheme; should be included; would be input	Cadastral database	External reference	Data source: Street registry of Statistics Austria; Address registry of BEV	Level 3			✓	X	X		
	Cadastral information	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3			X	X	X		
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Units (e.g. apartments) that are mapped in the EPC	Technician defined	Technician assumption	Based on planning documents for building permit; or inspection	Level 1			X	X	X		
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	No																		
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	light construction, medium heavy construction, heavy construction, very heavy construction	Technician defined	External reference		Level 2			X	X	X		
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	residential building 1 to 2 units, residential building 3 to 5 units, office building, educational institution, hospital, care home, etc.	Legislative or technical standard	External reference	OIB RL 6	Level 3			✓	X	X		
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	Yes	✓	X	X	General	Qualitative	Input	Information is available but not included in the current EPC scheme	Cadastral database	External reference	Data source: Land registry (Grundbuch) and input by expert	Level 3			✓	X	X		
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Technician assumption	Based on planning documents for building permit	Level 1			✓	X	X		
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	Yes	✓	X	X	General	Qualitative	Input	Information is available but not included in the current EPC scheme; should be included; would be input	Technician defined	Technician assumption	Based on planning documents for building permit; or inspection	Level 1			✓	X	X		
	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Yes	✓	X	✓	Climatic data	Qualitative	Input	North/West/Southeast/Central Alpine, South/Southeast, Southern	Legislative or technical standard	External reference	Austrian Standard B 8110-5:2019-03-15	Level 3			X	X	X		
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	Yes	✓	X	✓	Climatic data	Quantitative	Input	HGT14/22	Legislative or technical standard	External reference	Austrian Standard B 8110-5:2019-03-15	Level 3			✓	X	X		
EPC information on building at the current state	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Technician assumption	Based e.g. on planning documents for building permit	Level 1			✓	✓	X	Policy making, applicable also for the rows below	
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	or intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation		Level 1			✓	✓	X		
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	or intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation		Level 1			X	✓	X		
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			X	✓	X		
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	X	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	based on individual components; available as result of calculation program; input or intermediate	Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			X	X	X		
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	X	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	based on individual components; available as result of calculation program; input or intermediate	Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			X	X	X		
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	Yes	X	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Covered by calculation program	Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			X	X	X		
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	Yes	✓	X	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	Input or intermediate result depending on type of calculation method (simplified, detailed, mixed)	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation		Level 1			✓	✓	X		
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	X	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Available as result of calculation program based on individual components	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	X	X		
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	X	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Available as result of calculation program based on individual components	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	X	X		
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature	Yes	✓	X	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	Specific requirements must be met	Technician defined	Technician assumption	Product specification	Level 1			✓	✓	X		
	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	It depends on the specific case if data input is mandatory for the EPC	Technician defined	Technician assumption	Product specification	Level 1			X	✓	X		
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation	Yes	✓	X	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Output	Requirement must be met, according to OIB RL 6	NA	NA					✓	✓	X			

Data collection sheet - Croatia

Table 16. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Croatia)

	Contents						Data sources			Data quality			Data applications							
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>
	Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey		True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)		
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative			Cadastral database	External reference				✓	X	X		
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative			Based on occupant interview	Inspection				✓	✓	X		
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	No																	
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative			Statistical database	NA					X	✓	X	
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative			Statistical database	NA					X	✓	X	
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	No																	
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Cadastral information	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	No																	
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	External reference		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	No																	
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	External reference		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	X		
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	✓		
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Based on occupant interview	Inspection		Level 2		X	X	X		
	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Climatic data	Qualitative	Input		Statistical database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	No																		
EPC information on building at the current state	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	No																	
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	No																	
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	X		
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	No																	
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Technician defined	Detailed calculation				✓	✓	X		
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	No																	
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	No																	
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature.	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Technician defined	Detailed calculation				✓	✓	X		
Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	No																		
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input		Legislative or technical standard	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	X			

Table 17. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Croatia)

	Contents									Data sources			Data quality			Data applications					
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other	
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme															True (-) False (+) (optional)
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
	Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results					Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey			True (-) False (+)	True (-) False (+)	True (-) False (+)		
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	X		
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	X		
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	No																		
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	X		
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	No																		
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	No																		
EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Energy need for space cooling	Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	No																		
	Delivered energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the reported energy	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Exported energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	X		
	Exported energy carrier type	Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	No																		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	CO ₂ emissions	Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Environmental indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	X		
	SRI indicators	The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid	No																		
NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Legislative or technical standard	External reference					✓	✓	✓			
Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓			
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Technician defined	Inspection					✓	✓	X		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	No																		
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofitting options	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Economic information	Quantitative	Output		Technician defined	Inspection					✓	X	✓		
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	X	✓		
Additional EPC data																					
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex quantity derived as the complex average of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex	No																			
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/06/2015	No																			
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	No																			
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	No																			
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	No																			
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	No																			
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	No																			
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	No																			
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	No																			
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	No																			
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	No																			
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	No																			
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	No																			
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	No																			
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation	Yes	X	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	X			
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation	Yes	X	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Input		Legislative or technical standard	External reference		Level 3			X	X	X			
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation	No																			
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area	No																			

Data collection sheet - Cyprus

Table 18. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Cyprus)

	Contents						Data sources			Data quality			Data applications							
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
	Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey		True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)		
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and dataset	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								✓	X	X		
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								✓	X	X		
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								X	X	X		
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								X	X	X		
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	Yes	X	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								X	X	X		
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	No																	
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Qualitative		Geographical database	External reference					✓	✓	✓		
	Cadastral informations	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative		Cadastral database	External reference					✓	X	X		
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative		Cadastral database	External reference					✓	X	✓		
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative		Regional or national database	External reference					✓	X	✓		
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	X	General	Qualitative		Survey on-site	Inspection					✓	X	✓		
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								✓	X	X		
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	No																	
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	No																	
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	No																	
EPC information on building at the current state	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Climatic data	Qualitative	Input	Regional or national database	External reference		Level 3			✓	✓	✓		
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Climatic data	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	✓	X		
	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	No																	
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	No																	
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			X	✓	X		
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature.	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation		Level 1			X	✓	X		
Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	Legislative or technical standard	External reference		Level 3			X	✓	X			
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation		Level 1			✓	✓	✓			

Table 19. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Cyprus)

		Contents								Data sources			Data quality			Data applications				
Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other	
		Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme															
<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)		Brief description of the parameter				Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data			Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey				True (-) False (X) True (-) False (X) True (-) False (X)			
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state																				
Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Output	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service for the reference building are available in XML.	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	No																		
EPC results																				
Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Energy need for space heating for the reference building is available in both XML and RP database	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Energy need for space cooling	Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Energy need for space cooling for the reference building is available in both XML and RP database	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	No																		
Delivered energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the exported energy	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Exported energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	No																		
Exported energy carrier type	Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building	No																		
CO ₂ emissions	Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Environmental indicators	Quantitative	Output	CO ₂ emission per energy service for the real and for the reference/target building are available in XML.	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓	Environmental impact assessment	
SRI indicators	The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid	No																		
NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓		
Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓		
EPC information on building with improved state (recommendations)																				
Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓	Environmental impact assessment	
Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	No																		
Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofit options	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Economic information	Quantitative	Output	In the Italian EPC, the considered economic indicator is the payback period of the investment.	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓	Life Cycle Assessment	
Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment	No																		
Additional EPC data																				
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex quantity defined as the complex amplitude of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex amplitude of the temperature in zone m when the temperature in zone m is held constant	No																		
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/06/2015	No																		
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	No																		
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	No																		
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			X	✓	X		
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Legislative or technical standard	External reference		Level 3			X	✓	X		
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	Yes	✓	X	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	X		
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	Yes	✓	X	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	X		
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	✓	X		
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	No																		
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	General	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			X	✓	X		
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	No																		
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	No																		
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	Yes	✓	✓	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	X		
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation	No																		
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation	No																		
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation	No																		
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area	No																		

Data collection sheet - Italy (Piemonte region)

Table 20. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Italy)

	Contents										Data sources			Data quality			Data applications			
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list- (Look at caption)>	<Choice from list- (Look at caption)>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>
	Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme		Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation	Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty		True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)		
	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								✓	X	X		
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								✓	X	X		
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								X	X	X		
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative								X	X	X		
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	There are two elements for identifying the EPC: one for the XML cadaster and one for the open data							X	X	X		
EPC information on the assessed object and assessor	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Quantitative	Input		Geographical database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Qualitative	Input		Geographical database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Cadastral information	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	X		
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	✓		
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	Yes	X	✓	X	General	Qualitative	Input		Regional or national database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	✓		
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	X	General	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2		✓	X	✓		
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	X		
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	Yes	✓	✓	X	General	Qualitative	Input		Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	X	X		
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Regional or national database	External reference		#N/D		✓	X	✓		
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	Yes	✓	✓	X	General	Qualitative	Input		Regional or national database	External reference		#N/D		✓	X	✓		
General information about the building	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Climatic data	Qualitative	Input	Average monthly outdoor temperature, average monthly relative humidity, solar irradiance by...	Regional or national database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Climatic data	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				X	✓	X		
	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Net floor area per space is available in XML	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Net volume per space is available in XML	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Technician defined	Inspection				✓	✓	✓		
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				✓	✓	✓		
EPC information on building at the current state	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				✓	✓	✓		
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature.	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation	May be either detailed or simplified.			✓	✓	✓		
	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input		Legislative or technical standard	External reference	May be assessed through inspection, legislative or technical standard or through design document	Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation	No																	

Table 21. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Italy)

		Contents								Data sources			Data quality			Data applications			
Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
		Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	True (-) False (X) (optional)	True (-) False (X) (optional)	True (-) False (X) (optional)			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey		True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)		
<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	In the open database this input is not qualitative but logical (0,1)	Technician defined	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Output	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service for the reference building are available in XML	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Survey on-site	Inspection			✓	X	✓		
	EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Energy need for space heating for the reference building is available in both XML and RP database	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓	
Energy need for space cooling		Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	X	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Energy need for space cooling for the reference building is available in both XML and RP database	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator		Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service		The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Energy performance indicator per energy service for the reference building is available in both XML and RP database. For the real building in the RP database	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
Delivered energy per energy carrier		Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the exported energy	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
Exported energy per energy carrier		Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
Exported energy carrier type		Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building		Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building are available in both XML and RP database	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	✓	✓		
CO ₂ emissions		Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Environmental indicators	Quantitative	Output	CO ₂ emission per energy service for the real and for the reference target building are available in XML	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	X	✓	Environmental impact assessment	
SRI indicators		The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid	No																
NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output	Logical (0,1)	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	X	✓			
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	X	✓		
	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection	Level 2		✓	✓	✓	Environmental impact assessment	
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	X	✓		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	X	✓		
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofit options	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Economic informations	Quantitative	Output	In the Italian EPC, the considered economic indicator is the payback period of the investment	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			✓	X	✓	Life Cycle Assessment	
Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment	No																	
Additional EPC data																			
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex quantity defined as the complex amplitude of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex amplitude of the temperature in zone n when the temperature in zone m is held constant	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation			Level 1		X	X	X	
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/06/2015	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	X	X	
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input		Cadastre database	External reference					✓	✓	✓	
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	Yes	✓	X	X	General	Qualitative	Input	The cooling season is not defined by the Italian legislation	Legislative or technical standard	External reference			Level 3		X	✓	X	
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Technician assumption			Level 1		X	✓	X	
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Legislative or technical standard	External reference			Level 3		X	✓	X	
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	Yes	✓	X	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection			Level 2		✓	✓	X	
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	Yes	✓	X	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection			Level 2		✓	✓	X	
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	✓	X	
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection			Level 2		X	✓	X	
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	General	Quantitative	Input		Technician defined	Inspection			Level 2		X	✓	X	
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	Yes	✓	X	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					X	✓	X	
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Heat balance terms per space are available in XML. The heat balance terms for the whole building are available in XML	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	X	
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	Yes	✓	✓	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	X	
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation	No																	
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation	No																	
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation	No																	
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area	No																	

Data collection sheet - Slovenia

Table 22. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Slovenia)

Contents										Data sources			Data quality			Data applications			
Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
<i>Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)</i>	<i>Brief description of the parameter</i>	<i>Availability of the content</i>	<i>Availability of the content in the XML database</i>	<i>Availability of the content in the open access database</i>	<i>Availability of the content in the EPC scheme</i>			<i>Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation</i> <i>Output to be used only for final results</i>				<i>Automatic filled</i> <i>Level of uncertainty required only for input data</i>	<i>Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty</i> <i>Level of uncertainty required only for input data</i> <i>Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty</i> <i>Leave blank if the cell is grey</i>		<i>True (-) False (X)</i>	<i>True (-) False (X)</i>	<i>True (-) False (X)</i>		
<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative		Cadastral database	External reference				✓	X	X		
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	No																
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	No																
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative							X	X	X		
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative							X	X	X		
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Quantitative	Input	Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Qualitative	Input	Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3		✓	✓	✓		
	Cadastral information	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Cadastral database	External reference	Number of cadastral municipality and building number are quantitative, while parcel number is qualitative.	Level 3	Level 3	✓	X	X		
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3	Level 3	✓	X	✓		
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	External reference	In majority cases the data derive from project documentation. In very low percentage, the data must be measured on-site.	Level 2	Level 3	Level 2 for the cases where the project documentation is available, level 2 for all the rest.	✓	X	✓	
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	General	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	External reference	In majority cases the data derive from project documentation. In very low percentage, the data must be measured on-site.	Level 2	Level 3	Level 3 for the cases where the project documentation is available, level 2 for all the rest.	✓	X	✓	
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	External reference		Level 2	Level 3	Level 3 for the cases where the project documentation is available, level 2 for all the rest.	✓	X	X	
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	Yes	✓	✓	X	General	Quantitative	Input	Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3	Level 3		✓	X	X	
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Cadastral database	External reference		Level 3			✓	X	✓	
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	No																
EPC information on building at the current state	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Yes	✓	X	X	Climatic data	Qualitative	Input	Statistical database	External reference		Level 3	Level 3		✓	✓	✓	
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	Yes	✓	X	X	Climatic data	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Statistical database	External reference				X	✓	X		
	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2	Level 2		✓	✓	✓	
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2	Level 2		✓	✓	✓	
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	NA					✓	✓	✓	
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Technician defined	Inspection					✓	✓	✓	
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Technician defined	Inspection					✓	✓	✓	
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	✓	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2	Level 2		✓	✓	✓	
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	No																
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓	
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓	
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Yes	✓	✓	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓	
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature.	No																
Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	No																	
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation	Yes	X	X	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	X		

Table 23. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Slovenia)

Contents										Data sources			Data quality			Data applications				
Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other	
Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation Output to be used only for final results				Automatic filled Level of uncertainty required only for input data	Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty Level of uncertainty required only for input data Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty Leave blank if the cell is grey		True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)			
<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Choice from list> (Look at caption)	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	No																	
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input	Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	Yes	✓	✓	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input	Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	X	✓		
	EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓	
Energy need for space cooling		Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	X	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator		Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service		The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	No																	
Delivered energy per energy carrier		Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the expected energy	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Exported energy per energy carrier		Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
Exported energy carrier type		Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building		Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	✓	✓		
CO ₂ emissions		Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Environmental indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓		
SRI indicators		The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid	No																	
NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	No																		
Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation					✓	X	✓			
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM	No																	
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	No																	
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofitting options	No																	
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	X	✓		
Additional EPC data																				
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex quantity: inverse of the complex sum of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex sum of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone n	No																		
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/09/2015	No																		
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	No																		
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	No																		
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	No																		
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	No																		
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	No																		
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	No																		
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	No																		
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	No																		
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	No																		
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	No																		
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	No																		
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	No																		
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation	Yes	X	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				X	X	X			
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation	Yes	X	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				X	X	X			
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation	Yes	X	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				X	X	X			
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				✓	✓	✓			

Data collection sheet - Spain (Catalonia)

Table 24. Data collection sheet (Part 1, Spain)

	Contents										Data sources			Data quality			Data applications			
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>	
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and estimator	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative		Technician defined	Inspection					X	X	X		
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative		Technician defined	Inspection					✓	✓	✓		
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative		Technician defined	Technician assumption					✓	✓	✓		
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative		Technician defined	Technician assumption					X	X	✓		
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	Yes	X	✓	✓	General	Quantitative		Regional or national database	NA					X	X	X		
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	Yes	X	✓	X	Geographical information	Quantitative	Input	Geographical database	External reference		Level 3			✓	✓	✓		
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geographical information	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	X	✓		
	Cadastral information	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			✓	X	✓		
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	Yes	X	X	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection	The number of apartments of a block is in the inscription form of the register.	Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection	Types: single house, apartment block, one apartment of a block and tertiary (office, hospital, commercial...)	Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	Yes	X	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	External reference	This information is in the inscription form of the register (it's in the data base of the register, but it is not public nowadays).	Level 2			✓	X	X		
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	General	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	External reference		Level 2			✓	X	✓		
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	No																	
EPC information on building at the current state	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Climatic data	Qualitative	Input	Regional or national database	External reference		Level 3			✓	✓	✓		
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	No																	
	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	Yes	✓	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	Yes	✓	X	X	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Yes	✓	X	✓	Geometric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Geometric	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	No																	
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	No																	
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	No																	
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature.	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Technician defined	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	X		
Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	X	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	External reference		Level 2			✓	✓	✓			
Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation	Yes	✓	X	✓	Building fabric	Quantitative	Input	This data is in a PDF of verification of legislation.	Legislative or technical standard	External reference		Level 3			✓	✓	✓		

Table 25. Data collection sheet (Part 2, Spain)

	Contents									Data sources			Data quality			Data applications				
	Name	Description	Content database				Data category	Type	Input or output for energy calculation	Notes	Source type	Way of determination	Notes	Suggested level of uncertainty	Level of uncertainty	Notes	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Other
			Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme														
	<Free text>	<Free text>	<Yes/No>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Choice from list>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<Automatic filled>	<Choice from list>	<Free text>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<True or False>	<Free text>
	Identifying name for the parameter (only for new entries)	Brief description of the parameter	Availability of the content	Availability of the content in the XML database	Availability of the content in the open access database	Availability of the content in the EPC scheme			Required only for the parameters related to the energy performance calculation					Manual compilation in substitution of the suggested level of uncertainty			True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	True (-) False (X)	
									Output to be used only for final results					Level of uncertainty required only for input data						
														Level 1 represents the maximum uncertainty						
														Leave blank if the cell is grey						
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	Yes	✓	X	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	Yes	✓	X	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	X	✓	Technical building systems	Qualitative	Input	Survey on-site	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	X	✓	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Intermediate result	Technician defined	Inspection					✓	✓	✓		
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	Yes	✓	X	X	Technical building systems	Quantitative	Input	Technician defined	Inspection		Level 2			✓	✓	✓		
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	No																	
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	No																	
EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Energy need for space cooling	Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Delivered energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the exported energy	No																	
	Exported energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	No																	
	Exported energy carrier type	Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	No																	
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	CO2 emissions	Coefficient that describes the amount of CO2 that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Environmental indicators	Quantitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	SRI indicators	The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid	No																	
NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	No																		
Energy efficiency rating class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	Yes	✓	✓	✓	Energy indicators	Qualitative	Output	Numerical assessment	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓			
EPC information on buildings at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Input	Technician defined	Technician assumption		Level 1			✓	✓	✓		
	Energy efficiency rating class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating class of the recommended EEM	Yes	✓	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Technician defined	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	Yes	✓	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	Technician defined	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofitting options	Yes	✓	X	✓	Economic informations	Quantitative	Output	Technician defined	Detailed calculation					✓	✓	✓		
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment	Yes	✓	X	✓	General	Qualitative	Output	Technician defined	Detailed calculation					✓	X	✓		
Additional EPC data																				
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex energy density or the complex energy density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex thermal conductivity of the component	No																		
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/06/2015	No																		
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	No																		
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	No																		
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	No																		
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	No																		
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	No																		
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	No																		
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	No																		
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	No																		
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	No																		
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	No																		
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	No																		
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	No																		
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation	Yes	✓	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Intermediate result		Numerical assessment	Simplified calculation				✓	X	X			
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation	Yes	X	X	✓	Energy indicators	Quantitative	Output	It's in the verification of the legislation	Legislative or technical standard	External reference				✓	X	✓			
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation	No																		
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area	No																		

Annex B – Comparison tables

Table 26. EPC data availability comparison table (Part 1)

	Name	Description	ITALY			CROATIA			CYPRUS			SPAIN			SLOVENIA			AUSTRIA		
			POLITO / EDIC / RP			EIHP				CEA / CUT				FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE				JSI / MzI / GOLEA		
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	XML	OAD	EPC							XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Cadastral informations	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC			
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedure and/or energy performance	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC										XML	OAD	EPC
	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC

Table 27. EPC data availability comparison table (Part 2)

	Name	Description	ITALY			CROATIA			CYPRUS			SPAIN			SLOVENIA			AUSTRIA					
			POLITO / EDIC / RP			EIHP				CEA / CUT				FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE				JSI / MzI / GOLEA			SERA		
EPC information on building at the current state	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of air components or a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of air opaque components or a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of air transparent components or a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall, floor, window frame, window glazing, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	XML	OAD	EPC										XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC

Table 28. EPC data availability comparison table (Part 3)

	Name	Description	ITALY			CROATIA			CYPRUS			SPAIN			SLOVENIA			AUSTRIA					
			POLITO / EDIC / RP			EIHP				CEA / CUT				FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE				JSI / MzI / GOLEA			SERA		
EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Energy need for space cooling	Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	XML	OAD	EPC							XML	OAD	EPC									
	Delivered energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the exported energy	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Exported energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC							XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Exported energy carrier type	Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC						
	CO ₂ emissions	Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	SRI indicators	The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid																					
	NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC												
	Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC									
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	XML	OAD	EPC							XML	OAD	EPC									
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofitting options	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC									
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment				XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC						

Table 29. EPC data availability comparison table (Part 4)

Name	Description	ITALY			CROATIA			CYPRUS			SPAIN			SLOVENIA			AUSTRIA		
		POLITO / EDIC / RP			EIHP			CEA / CUT			FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE			JSI / Mzi / GOLEA			SERA		
Additional EPC data																			
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex quantity defined as the complex amplitude of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex amplitude of the temperature in zone n when the temperature in zone m is held constant	XML	OAD	EPC															
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/06/2015	XML	OAD	EPC															
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	XML	OAD	EPC															
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	XML	OAD	EPC															
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC									
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC									
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC									
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC									
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC									
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	XML	OAD	EPC															
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC									
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	XML	OAD	EPC															
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	XML	OAD	EPC															
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC						XML	OAD	EPC	
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation					XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC		
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation					XML	OAD	EPC				XML	OAD	EPC	XML	OAD	EPC		
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation														XML	OAD	EPC		
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area														XML	OAD	EPC		

Table 30. Data source and determination comparison table - detail of data by country (Part 1)

Cadastre database	Geographical database	Regional or national database	Statistical database	Survey on-site	Technician defined
External reference	External reference	External reference	External reference	Inspection	Inspection
Geographical location - SLOVENIA	Geographical location - ITALY - SPAIN - AUSTRIA	Building typology - ITALY	Climatic region - CROATIA - SLOVENIA	Building address - CROATIA	Building address - SPAIN
Building address - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA	Building address - ITALY	Year of construction - ITALY		Building constructive typology - ITALY	Number of building units - SPAIN
Cadastre information - ITALY - CROATIA - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA		Year of last renovation - ITALY		Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA	Building typology - SPAIN
Number of building units - ITALY - SLOVENIA		Climatic region - ITALY - CYPRUS - SPAIN		TBS energy carrier per energy service - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SPAIN - SLOVENIA	Building constructive typology - SPAIN
Building use - ITALY		TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service - AUSTRIA		TBS nominal power per energy service - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA	Building use - SPAIN
Information of building property - ITALY - CROATIA - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA				TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service - ITALY - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA	Thermally conditioned floor area - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SPAIN - SLOVENIA
Year of construction - CROATIA - SLOVENIA				TBS year of installation per energy service - SLOVENIA	Thermally conditioned gross volume - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SPAIN - SLOVENIA
					Compactness ratio - CROATIA - SPAIN
					Thermal envelope area - ITALY - CYPRUS - SPAIN
					Opaque thermal envelope area - ITALY - CYPRUS - SPAIN
					Transparent thermal envelope area - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SPAIN - SLOVENIA
					Thermal envelope area per exposure - CYPRUS - SPAIN
					Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope - SPAIN
					Energy services - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SPAIN - SLOVENIA
					Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service - SPAIN
					TBS nominal power per energy service - SPAIN
					Exported energy carrier type - ITALY - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA
					Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM) - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS - SLOVENIA
					Suggestion for the occupant awareness - CROATIA - SLOVENIA
					Ventilation airflow rate - CROATIA
					Lighting power density per space - CROATIA
					Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS
					Metering system - ITALY - CROATIA - CYPRUS
					Energy balance terms per sub-system - ITALY
					Heat balance terms per space or per building - ITALY - CYPRUS

Table 31. Data source and determination comparison table - detail of data by country (Part 2)

Technician defined	Technician defined	Legislative or technical standard	Based on occupant interview	Numerical assessment
Technician assumption	External reference	External reference	Inspection	Simplified calculation
Cadastre information - SPAIN	Building typology - CROATIA - SLOVENIA	Building use - AUSTRIA	Year of last renovation - CROATIA	Thermally conditioned gross volume - AUSTRIA
Number of building units - AUSTRIA	Building constructive typology - SLOVENIA - AUSTRIA	Climatic region - AUSTRIA		Compactness ratio - AUSTRIA
Year of construction - AUSTRIA	Building use - CROATIA - SLOVENIA	Degree days - AUSTRIA		Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope - AUSTRIA
Year of last renovation - AUSTRIA	Information of building property - SPAIN	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components - ITALY - CYPRUS		Thermal transmittance per building envelope component - CYPRUS
Thermally conditioned floor area - AUSTRIA	Year of construction - SPAIN	Building envelope thermal transmittance limit - CROATIA - SPAIN		Building envelope thermal transmittance limit - ITALY - CYPRUS
Thermal envelope area - AUSTRIA	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components - SPAIN	NZEB rating - SPAIN		TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service - AUSTRIA
Opaque thermal envelope area - AUSTRIA		TBS ID code per energy service - CROATIA		TBS ID code per energy service - ITALY
Transparent thermal envelope area - AUSTRIA		Thermal bridges - CROATIA		
Thermal envelope area per exposure - AUSTRIA		Ventilation airflow rate - ITALY - CYPRUS		
Thermal transmittance per building envelope component - AUSTRIA		Illuminance level per space - ITALY - CYPRUS		
Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components - AUSTRIA		Overall renewable energy performance indicator - CROATIA		
Energy services - AUSTRIA				
Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service - AUSTRIA				
TBS energy carrier per energy service - AUSTRIA				
TBS nominal power per energy service - AUSTRIA				
TBS year of installation per energy service - AUSTRIA				
Exported energy carrier type - AUSTRIA				
Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM) - SPAIN - AUSTRIA				
Heating and cooling season - CROATIA				
Lighting power density per space - ITALY - CYPRUS				

Table 32. *Input accuracy comparison table (Part 1)*

	Name	Description	ITALY	CROATIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN	SLOVENIA	AUSTRIA
			POLITO / EDIC / RP	EIHP	CEA / CUT	FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE	JSI / MzI / GOLEA	SERA
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	Building, part of a building or portfolio of buildings that is the object of the energy performance assessment	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Application type	Motivation for issuing the EPC (new construction, building renovation, rental, sale, etc.)	NA	NA	NA	NA		NA
	Adopted simulation software	Simulation software used to create the energy model	NA		NA	NA		NA
	Assessor's information	General information on the technician in charge	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	EPC ID code	Unique identifier for the EPC	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
General information about the building	Geographical location	Geographic location defined by the longitude and latitude	Input			Input	Input	Input
	Building address	Collection of information to give the location of the building	Input	Input	NA	Input	Input	Input
	Cadastral informations	General cadastral data on the properties listed in the cadastral databank	Input	Input	NA	Input	Input	Input
	Number of building units	Number of section, floor or apartment within a building which is designed or altered to be used separately from the rest of the building	Input		NA	Input	Input	Input
	Building typology	Certain size and geometry of a building (single-family house, terraced house, multi-family house, apartment block, etc.)	Input	Input	NA	Input	Input	
	Building constructive typology	Type of building construction (e.g. reinforced concrete skeleton, load-bearing masonry building, etc.)	Input		NA	Input	Input	Input
	Building use	Classification of buildings and/or building unit related to their main use or their special status, for the purpose of enabling differentiation of the energy performance assessment procedures and/or energy performance requirements	Input	Input	NA	Input	Input	Input
	Information of building property	Information about private or public property of the building	Input	Input		Input	Input	Input
	Year of construction	Year of construction of the building	Input	Input		Input	Input	Input
	Year of last renovation	Year of the last renovation of the building	Input	Input				Input
	Climatic region	Climatic area in which the simulated building is located	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	Degree days	Cumulative hourly temperature difference (sum of all hourly differences) between the outdoor air and a base temperature over a given period (heating or cooling season)	Intermediate result		Intermediate result		Intermediate result	Input

Table 33. *Input accuracy* comparison table (Part 2)

Name	Description	ITALY	CROATIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN	SLOVENIA	AUSTRIA
		POLITO / EDIC / RP	EIHP	CEA / CUT	FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE	JSI / Mzi / GOLEA	SERA
EPC information on building at the current state	Thermally conditioned floor area	Thermally conditioned floor area of the thermal zone	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	Volume inside the building envelope of the conditioned spaces measured on the exterior of the building	Input	Input		Input	Input
	Compactness ratio	Ratio between the thermal envelope area and the conditioned volume	Intermediate result	Input		Input	Intermediate result
	Thermal envelope area	Total area of all components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Input		Input	Input	Intermediate result
	Opaque thermal envelope area	Total area of all opaque components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Input		Input	Input	Intermediate result
	Transparent thermal envelope area	Total area of all transparent components of a building that enclose thermally conditioned spaces through which thermal energy is transferred, directly or indirectly, to or from the external environment	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	Area of the building envelope components that enclose thermally conditioned spaces per exposure (e.g. surface of wall or window facing North/South/etc.)	Intermediate result		Input	Input	
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of the total building envelope weighted on the envelope area	Intermediate result	Intermediate result	Intermediate result		Intermediate result
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Intermediate result		Intermediate result		Intermediate result
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	Average thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope weighted on their envelope area	Intermediate result		Intermediate result		Intermediate result
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	Thermal transmittance (U-value) of single components (i.e. wall, window, floor, door, etc.). It defines the ability of an element of structure to transmit heat under steady-state conditions, and it measures the heat flow through unit area in unit time per unit difference in temperature.	Intermediate result	Intermediate result	Input	Intermediate result	
	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	Thermo-physical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, density, thermal resistance, etc.) of the materials of which the building envelope components are made of (i.e. wall layers, window's frame, window's glazing, etc.)	Input		Input	Input	
	Building envelope thermal transmittance limit	Minimum thermal transmittance requirement according to National or Regional legislation		Input	Input	Input	Intermediate result
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	Heating, cooling, ventilation, de-humidification, domestic hot water, lighting, building automation and control, PV and wind as energy sources, etc.	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	Typology of TBS generator per energy service (e.g. condensing boiler, heat pump, PV system, chiller, etc.)	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	Energy carrier delivered to the TBS per energy service	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	Mean global seasonal efficiency of the TBS per energy service	Output		Output	Intermediate result	
	TBS nominal power per energy service	Nominal power of the TBS per energy service	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	Efficiency of part of a technical building system that performs a specific function (e.g. heat generation, heat distribution, heat emission)	Input		Input		Input
	TBS year of installation per energy service	Year of installation of generator per energy service	NA				Input

Table 34. Input accuracy comparison table (Part 3)

	Name	Description	ITALY	CROATIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN	SLOVENIA	AUSTRIA
			POLITO / EDIC / RP	EIHP	CEA / CUT	FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE	JSI / MzI / GOLEA	SERA
EPC results	Energy need for space heating	Heat to be delivered to a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output
	Energy need for space cooling	Heat to be extracted from a thermally conditioned space to maintain the intended space temperature conditions during a given period of time	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per unit of reference floor area	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	The overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service is an amount of the annual non-renewable primary energy use per energy service per unit of reference floor area	Output			Output		
	Delivered energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied to the technical building systems through the assessment boundary, to satisfy the uses taken into account or to produce the exported energy	Output	Output	Output		Output	Output
	Exported energy per energy carrier	Energy supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Output	Output			Output	Output
	Exported energy carrier type	Exported energy carrier supplied by the technical building systems through the assessment boundary	Input		Input		Input	Input
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator for the reference or target building	Output	Output		Output	Output	
	CO ₂ emissions	Coefficient that describes the amount of CO ₂ that is released from doing certain activity, such as burning one tonne of fuel in a furnace	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output
	SRI indicators	The SRI indicator rates the smart readiness of buildings (or building units) in their capability to optimise energy efficiency, adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and adapt to signals from the grid						
	NZEB rating	Specify if the building is considered NZEB	Output	Output	Output			
	Energy efficiency rating/class	Evaluation of the value of an energy performance indicator by comparison against one or more reference values	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output	Output
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	Recommendations for the improvement of energy efficiency with the proposal of the most cost-optimal interventions	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input	Input
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	Energy efficiency rating/class of the recommended EEM	Output	Output	Output	Output		
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the recommended EEM	Output			Output		
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	Economic indicator to determine and compare the cost-effectiveness of different building retrofitting options	Output	Output	Output	Output		
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness	Suggestion for occupants actions aimed to save money and reduce the impact of the building on the environment		Input		Output	Input	

Table 35. Input accuracy comparison table (Part 4)

Name	Description	ITALY	CROATIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN	SLOVENIA	AUSTRIA
		POLITO / EDIC / RP	EIHP	CEA / CUT	FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE	JSI / MzI / GOLEA	SERA
Additional EPC data							
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	Complex quantity defined as the complex amplitude of the density of heat flow rate through the surface of the component adjacent to zone m, divided by the complex amplitude of the temperature in zone n when the temperature in zone m is held constant	Input					
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	The summer effective solar area defines the summer behaviour of the transparent building envelope, according with the Italian M.D. 26/06/2015	Output					
TBS ID code per energy service	Unique identifier for the technical building system	NA					
Heating and cooling season	Period of the year during which a significant amount of energy for heating or cooling is needed	Input					
Thermal bridges	Thermal bridge properties (i.e. length of linear thermal bridge, linear thermal transmittance of linear thermal bridge)	Input		Input			
Ventilation airflow rate	Ventilation airflow rate per space or per whole building	Input		Input			
Lighting power density per space	The total input power of the installed lighting system per unit floor area per space	Input		Input			
Illuminance level per space	Amount of luminous flux per unit area	Input		Input			
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	Intermediate result		Intermediate result			
Metering system	Specify if the metering system is present	Input					
Thermally unconditioned zone	Thermally unconditioned zone properties (i.e. adjustment factor for the thermally unconditioned zone, solar heat gains in the thermally unconditioned zone, etc.)	Input		Input			
Energy balance terms per sub-system	Energy input, energy output, thermal losses and electrical consumption per energy service sub-system	Output					
Heat balance terms per space or per building	Heat balance terms (i.e. heat transfer by transmission, heat transfer by ventilation, sum of solar heat gains over the given period, etc.)	Output					
Energy need for domestic hot water	Energy need for domestic hot water	Output		Output			Output
Building energy need for heating limit	Maximum energy need for heating according to National legislation		Intermediate result		Intermediate result	Intermediate result	
Building primary energy limit	Maximum primary energy according to National legislation		Input		Output	Intermediate result	
Building energy cold limit	Minimal energy cold for cooling according to National legislation					Intermediate result	
Overall renewable energy performance indicator	Overall renewable energy performance indicator is an amount of the annual total renewable delivered energy per total heated floor area					Output	

Table 36. Overview of applications comparison table (Part 1)

Name	ITALY POLITO / EDIC / RP			CROATIA EIHP			CYPRUS CEA / CUT			SPAIN FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE			SLOVENIA JSI / MzI / GOLEA			AUSTRIA SERA			
	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	
EPC information on the assessed object, tool and assessor	Assessed object	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	X
	Application type	✓	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	✓	✓	✓				✓	X	X
	Adopted simulation software	X	X	X				X	X	X	✓	✓	✓				X	X	X
	Assessor's information	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X	X
	EPC ID code	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
General information about the building	Geographical location	✓	✓	✓							✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X
	Building address	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Cadastral informations	✓	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	X
	Number of building units	✓	X	✓				✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	X
	Building typology	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓			
	Building constructive typology	✓	X	✓				✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	X
	Building use	✓	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	X
	Information of building property	✓	X	X	✓	X	X				✓	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	X
	Year of construction	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓				✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X
	Year of last renovation	✓	X	✓	X	X	X										✓	X	X
	Climatic region	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X
Degree days	X	✓	X				X	✓	X				X	✓	X	✓	X	X	

Table 37. Overview of applications comparison table (Part 2)

Name	ITALY POLITO / EDIC / RP			CROATIA EIHP			CYPRUS CEA / CUT			SPAIN FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE			SLOVENIA JSI / MZI / GOLEA			AUSTRIA SERA		
	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys
EPC information on building at the current state	Thermally conditioned floor area	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Thermally conditioned gross volume	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Compactness ratio	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Thermal envelope area	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Opaque thermal envelope area	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Transparent thermal envelope area	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Thermal envelope area per exposure	✓	✓	✓				X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓				X	X
	Mean thermal transmittance of the total building envelope	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Mean thermal transmittance of opaque building envelope	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Mean thermal transmittance of transparent building envelope	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	X	X
	Thermal transmittance per building envelope component	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	✓	X				✓	✓
	Thermo-physical properties of the materials composing the envelope components	✓	✓	✓				X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓				X	X
	Building envelope thermal transmittance limit				✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	✓
EPC information on technical building systems at the current state	Energy services	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Technical building system (TBS) type of generator per energy service	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	TBS energy carrier per energy service	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	TBS mean global seasonal efficiency per energy service	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	X
	TBS nominal power per energy service	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	TBS subsystems efficiency per energy service	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	TBS year of installation per energy service	✓	X	✓										✓	X	✓	✓	X

Table 38. Overview of applications comparison table (Part 3)

Name	ITALY POLITO / EDIC / RP			CROATIA EIHP			CYPRUS CEA / CUT			SPAIN FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE			SLOVENIA JSI / Mzi / GOLEA			AUSTRIA SERA		
	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys
EPC results	Energy need for space heating	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Energy need for space cooling	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator per energy service	✓	✓	✓							✓	✓	✓					
	Delivered energy per energy carrier	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Exported energy per energy carrier	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X							✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Exported energy carrier type	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of the reference building	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
	CO ₂ emissions	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X
	SRI indicators																	
	NZEB rating	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓								
Energy efficiency rating/class	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X	
EPC information on building at the improved state (recommendations)	Recommended energy efficiency measure (EEM)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X
	Energy efficiency rating/class of recommended EEM	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓						
	Overall non-renewable energy performance indicator of recommended EEM	✓	X	✓							✓	✓	✓					
	Economic indicator of recommended EEM	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓					
	Suggestion for the occupant awareness				✓	X	✓				✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓		

Table 39. Overview of applications comparison table (Part 4)

Name	ITALY			CROATIA			CYPRUS			SPAIN			SLOVENIA			AUSTRIA		
	POLITO / EDIC / RP			EIHP			CEA / CUT			FUNITEC / ICAEN / CYPE			JSI / Mzi / GOLEA			SERA		
	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys	Energy & Environmental Statistics	Calibration or Validation	Market surveys
Additional EPC data																		
Periodic thermal transmittance of the opaque walls	X	X	X															
Summer effective solar area per unit floor area	X	X	X															
TBS ID code per energy service	✓	✓	✓															
Heating and cooling season	X	✓	X															
Thermal bridges	X	✓	X				X	✓	X									
Ventilation airflow rate	X	✓	X				X	✓	X									
Lighting power density per space	✓	✓	X				✓	✓	X									
Illuminance level per space	✓	✓	X				✓	✓	X									
Internal heat capacity of the building or building zone	X	✓	X				X	✓	X									
Metering system	X	✓	X															
Thermally unconditioned zone	X	✓	X				X	✓	X									
Energy balance terms per sub-system	X	✓	X															
Heat balance terms per space or per building	✓	✓	X															
Energy need for domestic hot water	✓	✓	X				✓	✓	X							✓	X	X
Building energy need for heating limit				✓	X	X				✓	X	X	X	X	X			
Building primary energy limit				X	X	X				✓	X	✓	X	X	X			
Building energy cold limit													X	X	X			
Overall renewable energy performance indicator													✓	✓	✓			

Annex C – Key terms and definitions

Accuracy: *the capability of an instrument to indicate the true value of measured quantity* (ASHRAE, 2014). Despite the accuracy usually refers to measurements, it is also applied to estimations, and thus it represents the capability of a model to provide the true value of an estimated quantity. In the context of the EPC data analysis carried out in TIMEPAC, the accuracy relates to data whenever they derive from measurements or estimations. The accuracy can be also considered as a reduction of uncertainty (see **uncertainty**).

Precision: *(a) indication of the closeness of agreement among repeated measurements of the same physical quantity; (b) amount by which a measured value is expected to deviate from the true value* (ASHRAE, 2014).

Uncertainty: *range or interval of doubt surrounding a measured or calculated value within which the true value is expected to fall within some degree of confidence* (ASHRAE, 2014). In the context of the EPC data analysis carried out in TIMEPAC, the uncertainty relates to EPC input and output data. To deal with the input data uncertainty, the source and way of data determination are included in the survey as they affect the uncertainty. The uncertainty of EPC outputs (energy indicators, mainly) is determined not only by input uncertainty, but also by the calculation method of the building energy performance (i.e. the model accuracy, see also **accuracy**).